

icosHELLS

**D1.3 LIVING LAB
GOVERNANCE
FRAMEWORK AND
TRAIN-OF-TRAINERS
SESSIONS**

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Executive Summary

The Mission Soil initiative aims to establish 100 Living Labs and Lighthouses by 2030, advancing soil health solutions through collaborative research and innovation. As part of this mission, the iCOSHELLS project is setting up six Living Labs, contributing to the broader framework of Soil Health Living Labs envisioned under Mission Soil.

This report supports the development of a joint governance structure and co-creation framework across the iCOSHELLS Living Labs, ensuring alignment with the Mission Soil. It is designed for iCOSHELLS Living Lab implementers and consortium partners while also serving as a reference for external stakeholders interested in Soil Health Living Labs. The report is complemented by a Train-of-Trainers series, which took place between January and March 2025. It transferred and discussed the report's key concepts with Living Lab implementers.

This report focuses on four key aspects:

1. Governance Framework

- The report outlines the governance framework developed collaboratively by project partners, building on previous deliverables:
 - **D1.2 (ATB):** Identifies success factors for iCOSHELLS Living Labs.
 - **D2.1 (GAIA):** Defines the operational structure of iCOSHELLS Living Labs.
 - **D3.1 (CETENMA):** Details soil health indicators for Living Lab experiments.
- It establishes key guiding principles ensuring coherence across iCOSHELLS Living Labs while allowing for local adaptations.
- It outlines the overall monitoring and evaluation system for iCOSHELLS based on the concepts developed in previous deliverables and this report.

2. Co-Creation Concept

- The report presents a structured co-creation concept that maintains consistency across Living Labs while allowing flexibility for local adaptation.
- It comprises eight co-creation sessions per Living Lab, engaging stakeholders in refining and evaluating soil health solutions as well as the development of the Living Lab.
- Practical guidance and templates ensure compliance with data management and ethical regulations while supporting interactive and inclusive co-creation processes.
- Partners from RISE have developed an approach and practical activities to promote soil literacy within the Living Labs, which are presented in this report.

3. Train-of-Trainers Programme

- To facilitate knowledge transfer, the report is complemented by a Train-of-Trainers programme, equipping Living Lab implementers with the necessary skills and fostering peer learning.
- The report provides an overview of the training concept and the three sessions conducted between January and March 2025.

4. European Reference Group – iCOSHINE

- The report conceptualises iCOSHINE, a peer-learning and knowledge co-creation platform for iCOSHELLS Living Labs and selected external experts.
- Four in-person and multiple online iCOSHINE sessions will be held, tailored to the needs of iCOSHELLS Living Labs and complementary to the SOIL-L activities.
- iCOSHINE will contribute to and be enriched by other iCOSHELLS Work Packages, particularly WP 5 (Solution’s replication and scaling up), WP 6 (Lessons-learned and Integration of LL in a wider context), and WP 7 (Communication, Dissemination Networking and Capacity building), enhancing the scalability, sustainability, and broader impact of iCOSHELLS.

Together with Deliverables D1.2, D2.1, and D3.1, this report lays the groundwork for local-level Living Lab activities. It particularly informs the implementation of co-creation efforts within and across Living Labs (WP1, Tasks 3 and 4). Additionally, it contributes to the operationalisation and implementation of the Living Labs in **Work Package 2**, the Monitoring and Evaluation of Living Lab experiments in **Work Package 3** and feeds into the continuous monitoring of Living Lab success in **Work Package 6**.

Introduction

Soil Health in the European Union

Healthy soils are the foundation for climate neutrality, zero pollution, a sustainable food supply, and a resilient environment. They act as carbon sinks, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, improve water quality, reduce the need for pesticides and fertilisers, and support biodiversity. In the EU, soil underpins 90% of all food, feed, fibre, and fuel production (EEA, 2023) and harbours over 25% of all biodiversity. Globally, terrestrial plants contribute an estimated 82% of calories in the human food supply, whilst terrestrial animals provide approximately 16% (FAO, 2019).

However, the European Union faces a serious soil health crisis, with 70% of soils in an unhealthy condition (Panagos et al., 2022) and 2.8 million potentially contaminated sites (Viera et al., 2024). The problems are widespread and complex: 21% of agricultural soils exceed drinking water limits for cadmium, 83% contain pesticide residues (with 58% containing two or more types), and 51% show mercury deposition. Additionally, 65 – 75% of agricultural soils are at risk of eutrophication from excessive nutrients, affecting soil and water quality and biodiversity (European Commission, n.d.).

Land use practices are increasingly unsustainable: only 13% of urban development uses recycled urban land, whilst 2.4% of soils are sealed (EEA, 2008). Agricultural soils are losing carbon at a rate of 0.5% per year, and 50% of drained peatlands are experiencing carbon loss. Unsustainable water erosion affects 24% of the land, and 23% has high subsoil compaction. Annual soil erosion totals approximately 1 billion tonnes (Akca et al., 2024). Between 2012 and 2018, the EU experienced a net loss of more than 400 km² of land per year (European Commission, 2021).

Land degradation is particularly severe in southern, central, and eastern Europe, where 25% of land was at high or very high risk of desertification in 2017—an 11% increase in just a decade (Vermann et al., 2020). The economic impact is significant, with soil degradation costing the EU over €50 billion annually. Despite these challenges, EU croplands and grasslands still provide €76 billion yearly in ecosystem services, and globally, halting and reversing soil degradation could yield up to €1.2 trillion annually in economic benefits (European Commission, 2021).

The Soil Strategy 2030

Launched in response to escalating threats to soil health, the EU Soil Strategy 2030 (European Commission, 2021) sets the ambitious goal of achieving healthy and sustainably used soils by 2050. This strategy is deeply integrated into the broader European Green Deal and the EU Biodiversity Strategy, emphasising the interconnectedness of environmental challenges. To achieve its goals, the strategy outlines several key actions. First, it proposes specific legislation for soil health, providing a legal framework for its protection and sustainable management. Second, it aims to promote sustainable soil management practices on the ground by offering free soil testing to landowners, enabling them to make informed decisions about their land. Third, it prioritises the protection of vital ecosystems such as wetlands and organic soils, recognising their crucial role in maintaining overall soil health. Fourth, the strategy introduces the concept of 'soil passports' to facilitate the safe and responsible reuse of clean soil,

promoting circularity and minimising waste. Finally, it highlights the importance of ongoing research and monitoring efforts to deepen our understanding of soil health and to track progress towards the 2050 target. Crucially, the strategy recognises that the success of these actions depends on effective collaboration between different stakeholders, including landowners, policy makers, researchers and industry.

A Soil Deal for Europe

The European Mission Soil, officially known as "A Soil Deal for Europe", part of Horizon Europe, complements these efforts by establishing 100 Living Labs and Lighthouses by 2030 (DG RTD, 2023). This mission focuses on eight key objectives (DG RTD, n.d.): reducing desertification; maintaining soil organic carbon stocks; preventing soil sealing; reducing pollution; preventing erosion; improving soil biodiversity; reducing the EU's global soil footprint; and enhancing soil literacy within society. The programme emphasises research, innovation, and public awareness through an ambitious research agenda with a strong social science component. Living Labs serve as real-world testing grounds where researchers, farmers, industry representatives, and other stakeholders collaborate to develop and validate innovative soil management practices. Lighthouses act as exemplary sites demonstrating successful implementations of sustainable soil management solutions, serving as beacons of best practice for others to follow. By developing a harmonised framework for soil monitoring across Europe, the initiative aims to create standardised methods for assessing soil health and tracking progress. This comprehensive approach combines practical experimentation, demonstration, monitoring, and public engagement to catalyse a transformation in how European soils are managed and protected, ultimately working towards the goal of achieving healthy soils by 2050.

The iCOSHELLS Project and Living Labs

The iCOSHELLS (innovative **CO**-creation for **Soil HE**alth in **Living Labs**) project is part of the Mission Soil and brings together diverse stakeholders to address the complex challenges of soil degradation, climate change and ecosystem vulnerability. By establishing six Living Labs on soil health across Europe, the project recognises the interconnectedness of soil health, ecosystem and societal well-being. Each Living Lab is anchored in a specific geographical context, recognising that soil health challenges vary greatly depending on location, climate, land use and historical factors. Furthermore, each Living Lab is tailored to its specific geographical context, addressing technical, social, economic and cultural factors that influence soil management practices.

The project spans different regions, from urbanised areas to agricultural landscapes, and fosters collaboration between research institutions, farmers, civil society organisations, educators, public authorities and small and medium-sized enterprises. iCOSHELLS uses innovative technologies such as remote sensing, precision farming and nature-based solutions to develop effective and sustainable soil health management strategies.

The Living Labs prioritise community engagement and co-creation, involving local communities in the design and implementation of solutions to ensure long-term success and sustainability. Robust ecological monitoring systems will track the impact of interventions, enabling continuous learning and adaptation. The project facilitates knowledge sharing and cross-fertilisation between the Living Labs, enabling replication and up-scaling of successful solutions across the European Union.

The iCOSHELLS project comprises six Soil Health Living Labs in six regions of the European Union. These are:

Basque Soil Health Living Lab

- Location: Basque County, Northern Spain and Southern France.
- Land use: Urban areas, interspersed with wetlands and wooded areas.
- Soil health challenges including flooding, erosion, pollution, poor soil structure, and the impacts of climate change.

Bulgarian Viticultural Soil Health Living Lab

- Location: Thracian Valley in Plovdiv Province, Southern Bulgaria.
- Land use: The predominant land use is agriculture, with a particular focus on grape and wine production.
- Soil health challenges: The primary soil health challenge is to enhance the resilience and mitigate the vulnerabilities of vineyard soils in the context of climate change.

Greek Mine Soil Health Living Lab

- Location: Western Macedonia, Northern Greek.
- Land use: Post-lignite mining areas.
- Soil health challenges: Soil restoration and reclamation of mining sites, particularly with high chromium and nickel levels.

Italian Soil Health Living Lab

- Location: Provinces of Emilia-Romagna, Lombardy, Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol, Veneto Northern Italy.
- Land use: Agricultural, orchard, and urban land use.
- Soil health challenges: All land uses face soil health challenges including soil carbon loss, urban soil sealing and pollution, poor soil structure, and loss of soil biodiversity.

Southeastern Spain Living Lab

- Location: Murcia Region, Southern Spain.
- Land use: Agricultural land use.
- Soil health challenges: Faces significant soil health degradation, impacting ecosystem resilience and challenging the pursuit of sustainable agriculture, particularly in intensive crop and woody crop areas.

SWEdish Soil Health Living Lab

- Location: Götaland, Southern Sweden.
- Land use in agriculture, encompassing both crop and animal production
- Soil health challenges include soil compaction, poor soil structure, reduced biodiversity, and nutrient imbalances, particularly concerning phosphorus deficiencies.

The iCOSHELLS Soil Health Living Labs provide a groundwork for establishing “Lighthouses,” which serve as exemplary sites for effective soil management and educational outreach. Unlike Living Labs, which focus on co-creation and stakeholder-driven innovation, Lighthouses are designed to showcase well-established practices and facilitate their adoption through training and knowledge sharing.

Purpose, Scope, and Target Group of this Report

Purpose

This report contributes to the development of a governance framework for Soil Health Living Labs within the iCOSHELLS project, building on the foundations laid in three previous deliverables. It extends the framework, with a particular focus on co-creation, and provides strategic and practical guidance for designing and implementing effective multi-stakeholder engagement processes.

The report also presents key findings from three Train-of-Trainers sessions held in iCOSHELLS to equip Living Lab partners with the knowledge and tools needed to implement co-creation processes. The sessions also introduced the overarching governance structure to ensure that all partners understand its different components and how co-creation fits into the wider governance framework. Finally, the report introduces the European Reference Group 'iCOSHINE', an institutionalised iCOSHELLS group that will facilitate ongoing knowledge exchange and collaboration between Living Labs, as well as with selected external experts and partner initiatives.

By providing these insights and tools, the report strengthens the implementation of co-creation processes in iCOSHELLS Living Labs and fosters a common understanding of Living Lab governance in iCOSHELLS. Furthermore, it supports alignment with the Mission Soil programme and its broader vision of Living Labs as key instruments for soil health innovation and collaborative research.

In addition to fostering a common approach, the report serves to build capacity among Living Lab partners by offering structured support for setting up co-creation processes tailored to their local contexts. While partners bring their own expertise and experience, this report provides additional methodological guidance and a structured framework to ease implementation and adaptation.

Finally, by sharing both methodological frameworks and practical implementation guidance, this report aims to contribute to the broader standardisation of Soil Health Living Lab approaches while still allowing for necessary regional adaptation. In doing so, it offers a model that other initiatives beyond iCOSHELLS can reference when designing governance and co-creation processes in their own Living Labs.

Scope

This report covers four key aspects of Living Lab governance and co-creation within the iCOSHELLS project:

1. Overall iCOSHELLS Governance Structure

The report complements the overall governance framework for iCOSHELLS Living Labs, developed collaboratively across project partners. It thereby builds on following Deliverables:

- **Deliverable 1.2 (ATB): Determination and Parameterisation of Success Factors for LLs**, which identifies success factors for iCOSHELLS Living Labs.
- **Deliverable 2.1 (GAIA): LL Operational Structure Document**, which defines the operational structure of iCOSHELLS Living Labs.
- **Deliverable 3.1 (CETENMA): Catalogue of Soil Health Indicators**, which details soil health indicators for the experiments conducted in the iCOSHELLS Living Labs.

The report contributes Guiding Principles for Soil Health Living Labs that ensure consistency across all iCOSHELLS Living Labs while allowing for local adaptation. These principles form the foundation for the co-creation process within iCOSHELLS. Furthermore, the report synthesises the collective impact of the previous deliverables into a unified monitoring and evaluation framework for iCOSHELLS.

2. Co-Creation in the iCOSHELLS Living Labs

Co-creation is central to iCOSHELLS, fostering collaboration between stakeholders to refine innovative, context-specific soil health solutions. This report outlines both the conceptual foundations and practical implementation of co-creation processes. It provides a detailed methodology, supported by structured procedures, templates, and methods, to strengthen the capability of Living Lab partners to effectively engage in co-creation.

3. Train-of-Trainers Programme

To build capacity and ensure effective knowledge transfer, the report highlights the Train-of-Trainers programme, designed to equip iCOSHELLS partners with the skills and resources necessary to plan and facilitate co-creation sessions. The programme also introduced the broader governance framework to ensure alignment and understanding across all partners. The design and structure of the programme are presented in detail.

4. European Reference Group: iCOSHINE

The report introduces 'iCOSHINE', an iCOSHELLS network that promotes knowledge sharing across the Living Labs. The platform facilitates collaboration and learning not only within the six iCOSHELLS Living Labs, but also with relevant external experts and initiatives. iCOSHINE also acts as a bridge to integrate iCOSHELLS findings into the wider soil health agenda, further strengthening the impact of the project.

Target Group

This report on Living Lab governance, co-creation processes, training methodology and European collaboration serves stakeholders across Europe and globally, with focus on six European regions. The target audience comprises three distinct yet interrelated groups.

The project consortium represents our primary stakeholder group, consisting of the partners implementing Living Labs, research institutions, expert organisations and Living Lab participants. These stakeholders will benefit from practical guidance on Living Lab governance, co-creation methodologies, and training materials to enhance their implementation efforts.

The Soil Deal for Europe Mission stakeholders form our second target group, including European Mission partners working towards 100 Living Labs by 2030, related soil health initiatives and policy bodies. These stakeholders will gain insights from Living Lab governance models, standardised co-creation approaches, training frameworks and European Reference Group activities, supporting their mission objectives.

The wider global soil health community encompasses Living Lab practitioners, facilitators, researchers, academics, policy makers and soil health initiatives. This diverse group will benefit from access to Living Lab governance models, co-creation tools, training materials and soil literacy frameworks, enabling them to adapt and implement these approaches in their respective contexts.

Governance of iCOSHELLS Living Labs

The governance framework for iCOSHELLS has been developed collaboratively across project partners, each contributing their expertise to different aspects of the framework. The overall structure is described across different deliverables, with each deliverable addressing specific elements of the governance model. Deliverable 1.2 (ATB) focuses on determining and parameterising success factors for Living Labs to evolve into Lighthouses, Deliverable 2.1 (GAIA) defines the operational structure of the iCOSHELLS Living Labs, and Deliverable 3.1 (CETENMA) details soil health indicators at experimental site level.

We build upon the work presented in the previous deliverables, adding further elements to the overall framework and synthesising their collective impact into a unified monitoring and evaluation framework for iCOSHELLS. This section provides an introduction to Soil Health Living Labs and its key purposes and derives key guiding principles that ensure consistency across all iCOSHELLS Living Labs. Furthermore, this section provides an overview of the iCOSHELLS Monitoring and Evaluation Framework. It outlines how the different governance elements presented in previous deliverables and in this report work together to ensure that the Living Labs can continuously learn and develop based on systematic and transparent monitoring and evaluation results.

The governance framework outlined in this report will serve as the basis for the long-term sustainability evaluation to be conducted in Work Package 6. The governance indicators, co-creation processes, and stakeholder involvement presented here will directly inform Work Package 6's assessment of the Living Labs' impact on soil health and socio-economic sustainability.

Purposes of Soil Health Living Labs

For the purpose of the mission "A Soil Deal for Europe", Soil Health Living Labs are defined as "user-centred, place-based and transdisciplinary research and innovation ecosystems that engage land managers, scientists and other relevant partners in systemic research and co-design, testing, monitoring and evaluation of solutions in real-life settings to improve their effectiveness for soil health and accelerate uptake" (European Commission, n.d.a). Living Labs are thus multi-stakeholder collaborations that operate and experiment on multiple sites at regional or sub-regional level. Individual sites could be, for example, urban green or industrial areas, companies and other locations where work is carried out and monitored under real-life conditions (ibid.).

Key purposes of Soil Health Living Labs include (European Commission, n.d.; n.d.a; 2021; 2002):

Innovation and Co-Creation: To foster the co-creation of practical, scalable, and user-centred solutions by involving diverse stakeholders in the innovation process.

Real-World Testing: To provide a real-world environment for testing and refining soil health technologies, practices, and policies, ensuring their effectiveness and adaptability to local conditions.

Knowledge Sharing: To facilitate the exchange of knowledge, best practices, and lessons learned among stakeholders, promoting interdisciplinary collaboration and learning.

Capacity Building: To enhance the skills and capacities of farmers, land managers, and other stakeholders in adopting sustainable soil management practices.

Policy Development: To inform and support the development of evidence-based policies and regulations that promote soil health and sustainability.

Public Engagement: To raise awareness and engage citizens in soil health initiatives, fostering a sense of ownership and responsibility for soil conservation.

Sustainability Goals: To contribute to the European Union’s and global sustainability goals, such as the European Green Deal, the EU Soil Strategy for 2030, and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 15 (Life on Land).

Guiding Principles for the iCOSHELLS Living Labs

To ensure a cohesive approach across the iCOSHELLS Living Labs that aligns with the Mission Soil understanding of Living Labs, we have developed a set of guiding principles for soil health Living Labs (see Figure 1). The principles are derived from relevant literature on Living Labs, particularly publications provided in the context of the Mission Soil initiative (DG RTD, 2023). The principles serve to provide clear direction for establishing and operating the Living Labs and co-creation activities within them, ensuring that all partners work towards a unified vision while accommodating the unique requirements of their respective environments.

Figure 1: Principles of Soil Health Living Labs.

Multi-Stakeholder Engagement in Living Labs

Successful Living Labs thrive on the collaboration of diverse stakeholders, including researchers, policy makers, agribusinesses, NGOs and farmers. By bringing together these different perspectives, Living Labs foster the co-creation of holistic and well-rounded solutions that address complex soil health challenges from multiple angles. This multi-stakeholder approach leverages diverse expertise and enables comprehensive problem solving that considers technical, social, economic and environmental dimensions. It also builds synergies across sectors, increasing the impact of initiatives and ensuring that solutions are scalable and sustainable. By bringing together diverse voices and resources, Living Labs create a collaborative ecosystem that drives innovation and meaningful progress in soil health and land management.

Figure 2: Multi Stakeholder Engagement in Soil Health Living Labs.

The User-Centred Approach of Soil Health Living Labs

Soil Health Living Labs adopt a user-centred approach that places end-users—such as farmers, agricultural workers and local communities—at the heart of the innovation process. These stakeholders are actively involved as equal partners throughout the co-creation, testing and evaluation phases. Their needs, experiences and insights are essential in shaping the development of tailored solutions that are practical, effective and responsive to real-world challenges. This approach ensures that the solutions developed are not only technically sound, but also relevant and actionable for the people who will ultimately use them. Ultimately, this user-centred focus helps bridge the gap between innovation and implementation, driving meaningful progress in soil health.

Real-Life Testing in Living Labs

Soil Health Living Labs develop and test solutions directly in the environments where they will be implemented. This hands-on approach ensures that innovations are practical, relevant and tailored to the specific conditions and challenges of the target area. Testing in real-world settings aligns innovations with real-world conditions, increasing the likelihood of success and adoption. It also allows for early identification of challenges, so that adjustments and improvements can be made before scaling up.

Co-Creating Solutions

In Soil Health Living Labs, diverse stakeholders collaborate to design, test, and refine innovations for soil protection and restoration. This process integrates multiple expertise and ensures that various stakeholder interests are considered from the outset. Soil users play a particularly important role, contributing to solutions that are both practical and relevant. Engaging key stakeholders early in the process fosters a sense of ownership, enhances adoption, and strengthens long-term commitment, ultimately supporting the successful implementation and sustainability of soil health innovations.

The Iterative Process in Soil Health Living Labs

The Soil Health Living Labs use an iterative approach where solutions are developed through cycles of experimentation, feedback and refinement. This process ensures that innovations are not only effective, but also user-friendly and responsive to end-user needs. The iterative nature of Living Labs helps reduce risk by identifying potential problems early in the development process. It also promotes continuous improvement, as feedback loops allow for ongoing adjustments and enhancements. By iteratively refining solutions, Living Labs ensure that the final outcomes are robust, practical and capable of making a meaningful impact on soil health and sustainable land management.

Soil Literacy: Building Awareness and Empowerment

Soil literacy involves raising awareness and understanding of soil health among diverse audiences through education and engagement. It empowers individuals to recognise the critical role of soil in ecosystem resilience, climate action and food security, and fosters a deeper appreciation for this vital resource. Engaged and informed communities are more likely to adopt and advocate for sustainable practices, driving collective action for soil conservation. Involving citizens into Living Lab activities bridges the gap between scientific knowledge and practical application, making soil health accessible to all. Importantly, soil literacy fosters a culture of long-term stewardship, ensuring that soil health remains a priority for current and future generations.

In this project, we have chosen to approach soil literacy from the more-than human perspective. It is a perspective that recognises that humans are not separate from nature, but part of an ecosystem of relationships with other living and non-living beings. The more-than human perspective sees soil as a dynamic, living entity rather than just a resource; it fosters coexistence with soil and emphasises the importance of soil health in building sustainable ecosystems. In practice, we use this perspective in dialogue with stakeholders, where we bring “soil” in as a stakeholder with its own needs and rights. We take personal, local, community and the systems perspective on soil to complement the technical project research and activities. This, to help us to understand our social, economic, and cultural connection, as well as reliance, on soil.

Building Comprehensive Monitoring and Evaluation Frameworks

Robust evaluation frameworks are essential for Soil Health Living Labs, involving baseline data, monitoring systems, and progress measurement across environmental, social, and economic dimensions. Aligned with the Mission Soil Implementation Plan, these frameworks enable site-specific assessments and cross-site comparisons to identify best practices and scalable solutions. They promote accountability, continuous improvement, and sustainable innovations that balance environmental health, social equity, and economic viability. Transparent results build stakeholder trust, foster collaboration, and facilitate knowledge sharing, accelerating progress towards Mission Soil’s goals.

Replication and Scaling

Replication and scaling expand successful soil health practices from Living Labs to broader areas, ensuring their sustainability beyond the project duration and applying them to regions with similar environmental conditions. This process is crucial for maximising the impact of Living Lab innovations, enabling long-term, widespread improvements in soil health. By integrating practices into local networks, policies, and advisory services, and fostering collaboration with stakeholders, solutions can be adapted to diverse contexts, driving systemic improvements in soil health management and contributing to sustainable land use at a larger scale.

The iCOSHELLS Monitoring and Evaluation Framework

The iCOSHELLS project implements a comprehensive, multi-faceted approach to monitoring and evaluation. This structured framework ensures that data collection and evaluation efforts are meaningful, consistent and support evidence-based decision making across all Living Labs.

The Monitoring and Evaluation framework covers different layers of Living Lab operations, each with a distinct but complementary function:

- 1. Living Lab Success and Readiness to turn into a Lighthouse (Outer Ring):** Led by ATB, this layer evaluates the overall performance of the Living Labs against established success criteria, synthesising insights from all other layers to provide a comprehensive assessment.
- 2. Co-Creation Success and Multi-Stakeholder Engagement (Middle Ring):** Led by CSCP, this layer evaluates multi-stakeholder co-creation sessions and engagement processes. It measures the quality and impact of collaborative activities that drive innovation within the Living Labs.

3. **Operational Excellence Layer (Inner Ring):** Led by GAIA, this layer monitors the implementation efficiency and operational standards of interventions. It establishes indicators that assess the progress of the experimental management structure.
4. **Soil Health Layer (Core):** Coordinated by CETNMA, this specialised layer focuses on soil health monitoring and environmental indicators, providing data on the success of soil health solutions.

The multi-layered approach strategically leverages the specialised expertise of different iCOSHells partners:

- **ATB:** Provides overarching evaluation methodology to synthesise success factors across Living Labs.
- **CSCP:** Applies stakeholder engagement expertise to evaluate co-creation processes and participation effectiveness.
- **GAIA:** Contributes operational excellence methodology to ensure efficient implementation.
- **CETNMA:** Brings environmental science expertise to lead soil health monitoring and environmental indicators assessment.

In addition, the governance data generated by this framework will be integrated into the wider data infrastructure developed in [D3.3 Web application and dataset architecture](#) focused on soil health monitoring. This integration will enable a holistic view of the Living Lab's performance, combining governance, operational and environmental data to support informed decision making and continuous improvement.

This section provides a brief overview of the monitoring and evaluation framework, building on deliverables D1.2, D2.1, and D3.1 and extending them to include the co-creation dimension. Further details can be found in the respective deliverables.

Living Lab Success and Readiness to turn into a Lighthouse

Success factors of Living Labs were developed in the context of deliverable [D1.2: Determination and parametrisation of success factors for LLs](#) by Richard Orozco, Trang Dam, and Philipp Grundmann from the Leibniz Institute for Agricultural Engineering and Bioeconomy (ATB). The following is a summary of the success factors. For more information, we refer the reader to D1.2 (Orozco et al., 2025).

1. **Strategic alignment and a shared vision** ensure that all stakeholders—farmers, researchers and policy makers—are working towards common goals. This alignment of resources, technologies and practices, such as regenerative agriculture, promotes a comprehensive approach to sustainable land management.
2. **Operational excellence** is important in managing complex environmental projects. Living Labs must continuously evaluate and adjust practices based on real-time data, such as soil pH and microbial activity. Flexibility in adapting methods, such as cover cropping or composting, and working with technology developers improves efficiency and effectiveness.
3. **Collaboration** plays a key role in driving innovation and sharing best practice. Partnerships enable the co-design of contextually relevant solutions, such as organic farming techniques, while inclusive stakeholder engagement ensures equity and relevance.
4. Successful implementation of soil health practices requires both **technical feasibility and strong community engagement**. Living Labs provide a platform to test interventions locally before scaling them regionally, supported by policy advocacy and public awareness campaigns.

5. **A clear steering structure** is essential for effective governance. Steering committees composed of different stakeholders, such as farmers and researchers, ensure coordinated decision-making, resource allocation and adaptability to new evidence or policy developments.
6. **Value co-creation** drives innovation and long-term success by ensuring that solutions are scientifically sound, socially acceptable and economically viable. **Collaborative efforts** in Living Labs lead to tangible benefits such as improved soil health and farmer knowledge, while also informing policy integration.
7. **Soil literacy** is a cornerstone of sustainable soil management. Higher levels of soil literacy correlate with better practices and greater willingness to adopt new technologies. Living Labs promote soil literacy through hands-on learning, workshops and real-time data sharing, fostering a deeper understanding of soil health among stakeholders.

The identified success factors will be monitored through survey questions and self-reporting mechanisms. A baseline analysis has already been carried out and the baseline data is detailed in the report by Orozco et al. (2025). To ensure continuous monitoring of progress, a structured framework for monitoring the development of these success factors is currently being developed. This framework will be communicated to the Living Labs as part of Work Package 6, providing a systematic approach to assessing and improving the effectiveness of the Living Labs throughout the project lifecycle.

This governance model will feed into Work Package 6 Task 6.2.2 by ensuring that ongoing evaluations track the performance of Living Labs against the key success factors identified in D1.2. Regular monitoring will enable adaptive management, ensuring that Living Labs evolve dynamically in response to emerging challenges and stakeholder needs.

Co-Creation Success and Multi-Stakeholder Engagement

The co-creation framework in the iCOSHells Living Labs is developed in the context of this deliverable (see Sec. [Co-Creation in the iCOSHells Living Labs](#)). Following aspects of the co-creation process will be monitored and evaluated across the iCOSHells Living Labs to stimulate continuous learning and improvement. A detailed description is provided in the next section.

- **Purpose of Each Session:** The specific objectives of each co-creation session and their alignment with the overall co-creation process within the Living Lab.
- **Multi-Stakeholder Participation:** Analysis of the diversity of participants, including their stakeholder groups and demographic characteristics.
- **Facilitation and Stakeholder Dynamics:** Evaluating facilitation methods, participant interactions and overall stakeholder dynamics within individual sessions and across the wider process.
- **Insights and Outcomes:** Documenting key insights and outcomes from each session and assessing their impact on the development and evolution of the Living Lab.

The monitoring and evaluation process will be carried out using the following tools and methods, which are detailed in the co-creation section of this report:

- **Session Reports:** Prepared by the Living Lab partner leading the session, these reports will include the agenda, meeting materials (e.g. presentations) and a summary of key discussions and outcomes.

- **Feedback Questionnaires:** Distributed to participants to capture their views on the structure, facilitation and outcomes of the session.
- **Anonymous Surveys:** Conducted during each session to collect high-level data on the structure of participants (e.g. stakeholder groups and demographic categories), while ensuring anonymity and compliance with consent requirements.
- **Participant List:** A record of participants to analyse participation trends and stakeholder representation.

Operational Excellence of the Living Labs

The operational structure of the iCOSHells Living Labs was developed in the context of deliverable [D2.1 Living Lab Operational Structure Document](#) by Begoña Benito and Daniel González (GAIA). For more information, we refer the reader to Benito & Gonzalez (2025).

To assess operational excellence, Benito & Gonzalez (2025) expanded the "operational excellence" success factor into nine indicators, which will be tracked as part of Work Package 2 throughout the iCOSHells project.

The indicators used in the operational structure of the Soil Health Living Labs include:

1. **Soil Health Efforts:** The overall commitment and actions taken to improve and sustain soil quality. This includes any practice that enhances the physical, chemical, and biological properties of soil, including biodiversity, to maintain or restore its productivity and resilience.
2. **Basic Workflows:** Standardised day-to-day operational processes that ensure consistency and reliability in managing Soil Health Living Lab activities.
3. **Processes for Soil Monitoring and Management:** The establishment and implementation of systematic procedures for sampling, analysing, and evaluating soil indicators, informed by CETENMA (WP3).
4. **Consistent Tracking of Soil Health Indicators:** Ensuring that data collection and analysis follow uniform methods over time, enabling reliable trend analysis and comparison.
5. **Processes Refined Periodically:** The ability of operational processes to evolve based on feedback from interactions within the Living Labs and among Living Lab Offices, ensuring continuous improvement.
6. **Integration of Digital Tools:** The use of sensors, data management systems (developed by UPM), remote sensing technologies, and decision-support systems to enhance data collection, analysis, and communication.
7. **Processes Register Feedback and Challenges:** The iterative Living Lab approach relies on systematically recording feedback and identifying emerging challenges to enhance operational effectiveness. Systems must be in place to document and adjust processes accordingly.
8. **Scalability of Operations:** The ability to expand or replicate Living Lab processes and technologies across different regions or operational scales while maintaining efficiency and effectiveness.
9. **Optimisation of Workflows:** Building on Basic Workflows, optimisation focuses on continuously improving resource utilization, effectiveness, and productivity.

These indicators will be monitored with the help of report templates that Living Lab partners fill in regularly (Benito & Gonzalez, 2025, p. 39). Reports will be shared with all relevant stakeholders and project partners through the project online SharePoint.

Soil Health in the Experimental Sites

A monitoring system for soil health in the experimental sites was developed in the context of deliverable [D3.1 Catalogue of Soil Health Indicators](#) by Cristiano Pisani and José M. Soriano Disla (CETENMA). The following is a summary of the developed soil health indicators. For more information, we refer the reader to D3.1 (Pisani & Soriano Disla, 2025).

Physical Indicators

- **Bulk Density:** Measures soil compaction and porosity; higher values restrict root growth and water infiltration.
- **Particle Size Distribution:** Determines soil texture (sand, silt, clay); influences water retention, root growth, and microbial activity.
- **Soil Water Holding Capacity (WHC):** Indicates the soil's ability to retain water; crucial for plant growth and nutrient mobility.

Chemical Indicators

- **Soil pH:** Measures soil acidity or alkalinity; affects nutrient availability and microbial activity.
- **Electrical Conductivity (EC):** Assesses soil salinity; high values can harm plant health and degrade soil quality.
- **Plant Available Macronutrients:** Measures essential nutrients (N, P, K, Ca, Mg, S); ensures optimal plant growth and productivity.
- **Total Nitrogen (TN):** Represents all nitrogen forms in soil; influences fertiliser use and microbial activity.
- **Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC):** Indicates soil's ability to hold nutrients (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , K^{+}); essential for plant nutrient supply.
- **Heavy Metals:** Assesses contamination risks; high levels threaten soil health and living organisms.
- **Soil Organic Matter (SOM):** Measures organic carbon content; enhances soil structure, water retention, and nutrient cycling.

Biological Indicators

- **Microbial Biodiversity:** Evaluates soil microbial communities; reflects soil health and ecosystem functioning.
- **Microbial Respiration:** Measures CO_2 release from soil; indicates biological activity and effectiveness of management practices.

In addition, site-specific indicators are collected in each Living Lab. All indicators are collected using a sampling protocol. Data will be stored in an online data platform. For more information, see Pisani & Soriano Disla (2025).

Co-Creation in the iCOSHELLS Living Labs

This section focuses on the co-creation aspect of iCOSHELLS Living Labs, which is at the heart of Work Package 1. It begins by outlining the purpose and benefits of co-creation for soil health living labs. Building on the guiding principles established in the previous section, it then outlines a co-creation process tailored for iCOSHELLS and provides practical guidance on planning and implementing co-creation sessions. It also provides a dedicated section on how to promote soil literacy in co-creation sessions building on the more-than-human approach. In doing so, this section ensures that co-creation activities in iCOSHELLS maintain a coherent structure while allowing for local flexibility and adaptation to specific contexts.

Purposes and Benefits of Co-Creation

Co-creation is a collaborative process where stakeholders—researchers, practitioners, end-users, policymakers, and communities—work together to design and implement tailored, sustainable solutions. It emphasises shared ownership, active participation, and integrating diverse perspectives (Voorberg et al., 2014) to ensure results are practical, relevant, and widely adopted. In the context of Mission Soil and Living Labs, co-creation involves farmers, scientists, companies, and local authorities in developing soil health innovations, ensuring they address real needs and conditions. This approach bridges gaps between research, policy, and practice, fostering sustainable soil management.

Co-creation is particularly effective in complex scenarios, such as policy-making or designing sustainable products and services (Sanders & Stappers, 2008), where diverse perspectives are essential to balance trade-offs and ensure inclusivity. It enables producers to coordinate closely with users, suppliers, and other stakeholders across the value chain, ensuring solutions align with user behaviour, environmental impacts, and lifecycle considerations. This process promotes innovation, balances technical feasibility with user acceptance, and enhances the overall sustainability of outcomes. Moreover, co-creation is indispensable for addressing systemic challenges that require buy-in from multiple stakeholders, cross-sector collaboration, or cultural and behavioural change (Orcik et al, 2013). It ensures that solutions are not only effective but also scalable and transferable across different contexts, driving long-term sustainability transformations.

Benefits of Co-Creation:

Fosters Openness to Innovation: Engaging diverse stakeholders cultivates adaptability and creativity, encouraging the adoption of new ideas and approaches.

Enhances Efficiency: Direct involvement of end-users ensures solutions align with real-world needs, reducing misinterpretation and increasing user satisfaction.

Boosts Motivation and Engagement: Active participation fosters a sense of ownership, increasing stakeholder investment and commitment to the process.

Accelerates Development: Rapid prototyping and feedback loops enable quick identification of promising ideas and potential issues, saving time and resources.

Reduces Failure Risks: Continuous feedback helps address issues early, minimising the risk of solutions failing to meet user needs.

Drives Sustainable Outcomes: Integrating diverse perspectives ensures solutions are scalable, adaptable, and sustainable across different environments.

The iCOSHELLS Co-Creation Process

Within the iCOSHELLS, co-creation is the fundamental development and innovation process in the Living Labs and supports them in all phases of development. Throughout the entire process, the living labs work according to the principles described in Sec. [Guiding Principles for the iCOSHELLS Living Labs](#). On the one hand, this ensures that the various local stakeholders are involved in the work of the Living Labs and that the development, testing and refinement of solutions for soil health takes place collaboratively, taking into account all user interests. Although not all aspects of the Living Labs and stakeholders can necessarily be considered in every Living Lab meeting, the entire co-creation process should be in line with the guiding principles of the Living Labs. Through the inclusive nature of soil health, a holistic understanding of soil health is achieved. Through further monitoring and evaluation (Subse. [iCOSHELLS Monitoring and Evaluation Framework](#)) successful solutions can be replicated and scaled up. The co-creation process, which comprises eight sessions in each Living Lab, is divided into two parts. An experimental part and an evaluative part, which accompanies the testing of the soil health solutions in three iterations, each lasting one year.

- Six sessions focus on the development, testing, validation and refinement of experiments to ensure that innovative solutions are rigorously evaluated and optimised.
- Two sessions are dedicated to assessing the progress of the Living Labs and reviewing the effective achievement of objectives.

The co-creation process is adapted to the specific context and needs of each Living Lab, taking into account that the labs are at different stages of development and have different challenges in implementing co-creation, as the analysis in Deliverables 1.1 and 2.1 have shown. For example, some labs have already selected concrete solutions for testing, while others are still in the process of defining their test locations. As the process progresses, the selection of participants and venues will be designed to match the specific objectives and focus of each co-creation event. In addition, the co-creation process itself will be further developed in response to the monitoring and evaluation results to promote continuous learning and improvement.

Key Roles of Co-Creation in Living Labs

The co-creation sessions have different foci in the course of the development of Living Labs (see Figure 3 for an overview):

Figure 3: Iterative Process for Soil Health Solutions: From Identification to Implementation.

- Initially, meetings can be used to brainstorm and select soil health solutions or to further develop and adapt existing approaches to the project.
- Later on, co-creation supports the planning of the implementation of solutions, the involvement of other stakeholders and the promotion of understanding of soil health.
- After the first round of experimentation, meetings can focus on collecting data for monitoring and evaluation, and reflecting on the results together.
- In preparation for further iterations, co-creation supports the refinement of solutions, the abandonment of ineffective approaches and the introduction of new ideas.

Table 1 gives an exemplary overview of a co-creative process in a living lab.

No.	Time	Purpose	Participating Stakeholders
1	03/25	Refine solutions to be tested	Farmers, tech. suppliers, researchers
2	05/25	Raise awareness, engage on soil literacy, and plan implementation	Farmers, tech. suppliers, researchers, citizens
3	12/25	Assess LL progress and goal achievement	all groups
4	02/26	Engage on soil literacy and co-create policy implications	Farmers, tech. suppliers, researchers, policymakers
5	03/26	Assess and refine tested solutions	all groups
6	12/26	Assess LL progress and goal achievement	all groups
7	03/27	Assess and refine tested solutions	all groups
8	12/27	Co-create future of the LL after iCOSHells ends	all groups

Table 1: Example of the Co-Creation Process in a Living Lab.

Planning and Facilitating Co-Creation Sessions

This section provides a comprehensive overview of the activities and steps to consider when planning and conducting co-creation sessions, whether in-person or online. We offer templates to address formalities and resources for facilitation techniques that local implementers can adapt according to their specific needs and contexts. Our aim is to guide Living Lab implementers through the practical implementation of co-creation within the iCOSHells framework, ensuring both structure and flexibility in their approach.

Planning a Co-Creation Session

Effective co-creation requires thoughtful preparation to ensure meaningful engagement and productive outcomes. This section outlines key steps and considerations for planning a co-creation session, from setting clear goals and identifying participants to choosing the right format and logistics. By systematically addressing these elements, Living Lab implementers can create an environment that fosters collaboration, inclusivity and innovation, in line with the objectives of the iCOSHells Living Labs.

1. Goal/Focus of the Co-Creation Session

- **Define the Goal:** Clearly articulate the goal of the session and make sure it aligns with the current status and future needs of the Living Lab. Whether the goal is to develop solutions, refine prototypes or evaluate results, the goal should be specific and actionable.
- **Guiding principles:** Ensure that the event adheres to the guiding principles of Living Labs, such as user-centricity, real-world experimentation and multi-stakeholder collaboration. This ensures that the session contributes meaningfully to the broader mission of the Living Lab.

2. Participants in the Co-Creation Session

- **Identify Important Stakeholders:** Invite participants whose expertise, perspectives and experiences are important to achieving the session objectives and who will facilitate dialogue among session participants. This includes researchers, practitioners, policy makers and end users.
- **Include Multiple Stakeholders:** Promote inclusivity by ensuring that different stakeholder groups are represented in the meetings, so they enrich the discussions. This in turn leads to co-creative, more holistic solutions.
- **Land Users:** Prioritise the involvement of land users—such as farmers, landowners and environmental experts—in meetings that focus on defining, developing and refining solutions. First-hand experience is particularly important when it comes to achieving practical and scalable results.

3. Location and Format of the Meeting

- **Location Selection:** Choose a location that encourages active participation and engagement. Consider factors such as accessibility, convenience and the availability of necessary resources.
- **Site Visits:** When possible, schedule site visits to give participants a deeper connection to the ground and the specific context of the Living Lab's work. This can improve understanding and inspire innovative ideas.
- **In-Person vs. Online:** In-person sessions facilitate face-to-face interaction and relationship building, while online sessions offer flexibility and can broaden participation geographically. Choose the format that best suits the objectives of the meeting and the needs of the participants.

4. Meeting Date and Time

- **Optimal Scheduling:** Choose a date and time that will maximise attendance and accommodate the schedules of key participants.
- **Duration:** Determine the length of the meeting based on the objectives. For longer sessions, consider breaking them into smaller, more manageable chunks to maintain focus and avoid participant fatigue.

5. Language of the Meeting

- **Choice of Language:** Choose a language that allows for clear communication and active participation of participants. The local language is often the best choice as it promotes comfort and fluency.
- **English as an Option:** If all participants are fluent in English and there are international participants or speakers, English can serve as a common language to facilitate broader communication.

6. Roles and Responsibilities in the Meeting

- **Define Roles:** Clearly define the roles and responsibilities within the Living Lab team for the co-creation activities. This includes tasks such as designing the meeting, organising logistics, inviting participants, preparing materials and documenting results.

- **Use Networks:** Identify and use existing networks within the Living Lab team to effectively engage stakeholders. This will ensure diverse representation and broaden participation.
- **Fill Gaps:** Identify any gaps in stakeholder representation and develop strategies to engage under-represented groups to ensure inclusion and equity in the co-design process.

Materials for Planning a Co-Creation Session

Readers will find in the Appendix a comprehensive [Co-Creation Session Script Template](#). This template allows Living Lab leaders to systematically outline key details for each session, ensuring clarity and alignment with the session’s objectives. It additionally includes a table to plan the agenda and facilitation methodology within the meeting. The table provides space to specify agenda points and select appropriate facilitation methods for each topic, ensuring structured and engaging discussions. For a deeper understanding of how to use this effectively, refer to the subsection on [Facilitating a Co-Creation Session](#) in the following.

Preparing a Co-Creation Session

The preparation of a co-creation meeting consists of three main components:

1. the development of content and facilitation methods for the meeting,
2. the organisation of the meeting in terms of logistics and participant management, and
3. the preparation of the formalities necessary for the meeting to be recognised as an official iCOSHELLS co-creation meeting.

To support this process and ensure coherence across iCOSHELLS Living Labs, we provide general guidance and templates for the formal requirements that all co-creation sessions must meet to be recognised as official iCOSHELLS co-creation sessions. Additionally, the following subsection of the report provides further insights on how to facilitate active engagement and how to promote soil literacy in co-creation sessions.

Points to consider when preparing a co-creation session

1. Meeting Preparation and Materials

- **Prepare Materials:** Ensure that all necessary materials such as agendas, presentation slides, handouts and prototyping tools are prepared in advance. This will help maintain the flow of the session and keep participants engaged.
- **Pre-Session Communication:** Send detailed information about the session objectives, agenda and expectations to participants in advance. This allows them to come prepared and contributes to a more productive session.

2. Facilitation Techniques

- **Role of the Facilitator:** Appoint a skilled facilitator to guide the meeting and ensure that discussions stay on track, all voices are heard and objectives are met. The facilitator should be neutral and skilled in managing group dynamics.

- **Interactive Methods:** Use interactive methods such as brainstorming, or design thinking exercises to stimulate creativity and collaboration. These techniques can help break the ice and encourage active participation.

3. Document and Follow Up

- **Document Results:** Assign someone to document the meeting's key points, decisions and action items. This will ensure that the insights and ideas generated during the session are captured and can be referred to later.
- **Follow-up Actions:** Develop a clear plan for follow-up, including assigning responsibilities and setting deadlines. This will help maintain momentum and ensure that the outcomes of the meeting lead to tangible results.

4. Evaluation and Feedback

- **Evaluate the Session:** Include a mechanism for evaluating the effectiveness of the session, such as feedback forms or a debriefing discussion. This will help identify what worked well and what could be improved for future sessions.
- **Participant Feedback:** Gather feedback from participants about their experience, including the organisation, facilitation and outcomes of the session. This can provide valuable insights for refining future co-creation sessions. See also next subsection [Formalities for Co-Creation Sessions](#).

5. Technology and Tools

- **Digital Tools:** If the session is online or hybrid, ensure that the necessary digital tools (e.g. videoconferencing software, collaboration platforms) are selected and tested in advance to avoid technical problems.
- **Prototyping Tools:** Provide access to tools and resources that participants can use to create prototypes or mock-ups during the session. This can make the co-creation process more tangible and productive.

6. Cultural Sensitivity

- **Cultural Considerations:** Be aware of cultural and societal differences among participants, especially when Living Lab sessions include very diverse groups. This includes understanding cultural and societal norms, communication styles and potential sensitivities to ensure a respectful and inclusive environment.

7. Risk Management

- **Contingency Planning:** Identify potential risks or challenges (e.g. technical problems, participants dropping out) and develop contingency plans to deal with them. This will help ensure that the meeting runs smoothly even if unexpected problems arise.

8. Legal and Ethical Considerations

- **Ethical Guidelines:** Ensure that the session adheres to ethical guidelines, especially if vulnerable groups are involved or sensitive issues are discussed.
- **Legal Considerations:** The Living Lab co-creation sessions have to comply with the European General Data Protection Regulation. See subsection Formalities for Co-Creation Sessions for a template.

Formalities for Co-Creation Sessions

To ensure compliance with legal requirements, ethical standards and project reporting obligations, Living Lab partners must adhere to the following formalities for each co-creation session:

1. Consent Form

- **Purpose:** To comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), all participants must sign a consent form before participating in the session. This ensures transparency and protects participants' personal data.
- **Template:** A GDPR-compliant consent form template is provided in the Appendix: [TEMPLATE FOR CONSENT FORM CO-CREATION SESSIONS](#). It has been developed in collaboration with the iCOSHELLS data management officer, ethics advisors and project coordinators.
- **Adaptation:** Some sections of the template will need to be adapted to the specific context of the Living Lab and co-creation session. If Living Lab partners wish to modify other parts of the template, they should contact the iCOSHELLS team for approval. Additionally, please translate the form into the local language used in your Living Lab.

2. Participant List

- **Purpose:** In order to report the success of the co-creation activities to the EU, Living Lab partners need to keep a list of participants for each session.
- **Format:** Participant lists can be produced in either physical or virtual formats. For online sessions, a screenshot of the list of participants of the meeting is acceptable.
- **Template:** A template is provided in the Appendix: [TEMPLATE FOR CO-CREATION PARTICIPANTS LIST](#).

3. Anonymous (Virtual) Survey for Participant Characteristics

- **Purpose:** In order to minimise the collection of personal data while still gathering essential information, Living Lab partners should use an anonymous survey to collect participant characteristics, such as stakeholder group affiliation and basic demographic data.
- **Format:** The survey should be conducted virtually to ensure anonymity and ease of participation.
- **Template:** A survey template is provided in the Appendix: [TEMPLATE FOR CO-CREATION PARTICIPANTS SURVEY](#). This template can be adapted into an online survey to be completed by participants during the session.

4. Feedback Survey

- **Purpose:** To monitor and evaluate the success of the co-creation process and to continuously improve future sessions, feedback should be collected from participants.
- **Template:** A customisable feedback survey template is provided in the Appendix: [TEMPLATE FOR CO-CREATION FEEDBACK QUESTIONNAIRE](#). Living Lab partners are encouraged to adapt it to their specific context and language, ensuring that key evaluation metrics are included.

Facilitating a Co-Creation Session

The essence of co-creation lies in the collaborative effort of multiple stakeholders to develop solutions or ideas together. A key challenge in any session is to actively engage participants so that they can contribute meaningfully to the process. To achieve this, careful planning of facilitation methods is essential. This section provides guidance on how to effectively structure and facilitate co-creation sessions to ensure that participants are included and engaged, discussions are productive and outcomes are impactful.

To encourage active participation, it is important to think strategically about how to facilitate each agenda item in the session. The second page of the [Co-Creation Session Script Template](#) contains a grid line specifically designed for this purpose. Here facilitators can plan interactive methods for each agenda item to ensure that the session is dynamic and engaging.

When selecting and planning facilitation methods, consider the following:

Materials Needed: Define in advance the materials needed to implement each method, such as flipcharts, sticky notes, digital tools or prototyping resources.

Roles and Responsibilities: Assign clear roles to facilitators or moderators to ensure smooth implementation of each method. For example, one facilitator might lead the discussion while another documents key points.

Selected Facilitation Methods

To support Living Lab facilitators, we have compiled and developed a range of facilitation methods that are well suited to stimulate interaction in soil health co-creation sessions. These methods have been selected to provide variety and to cater for different levels of complexity and group sizes. In addition, most of the methods can be adapted for both face-to-face and online sessions, ensuring flexibility across formats. A presentation of the following methods with instructions for practical implementation within the co-creation sessions can be found in the Appendix: [INTERACTIVE CO-CREATION METHODS](#).

Brainstorming and Affinity Mapping

Brainstorming is a creative technique designed to generate a wide range of ideas on a given topic in a short period of time. Participants are encouraged to think freely and suggest ideas without immediate evaluation or criticism, fostering an open and inclusive environment. The method is effective with both small and large groups. After brainstorming, affinity mapping (also known as affinity diagramming) is used to organise the ideas generated. Participants group similar ideas into clusters based on their natural relationships, which helps to diagnose complex situations and identify common themes. This structured approach helps to make sense of large amounts of data and is particularly useful for larger groups.

Dot Voting

Dot voting, also known as 'multi-voting' or 'dotmocracy', is a facilitation method used to prioritise options or make collective decisions. Participants are given a certain number of stickers or dots and place them next to the options they prefer. The options with the most dots are considered the group's priorities. This technique is simple, transparent and effective with both small and large groups.

Conversation Starters

Conversation starters are prompts or questions designed to start a dialogue on a particular topic. They are used to stimulate discussion, encourage participants to share perspectives and to explore issues in depth. This method is versatile and can be adapted for both small and large groups.

World Café

The World Café is a structured conversation process designed to facilitate open and intimate discussions and to link ideas within a larger group to access collective intelligence. Participants divide into smaller groups and discuss a topic at several tables, with individuals periodically changing tables and bringing their previous discussion to the new table. This method is particularly effective with larger groups (more than 15 people).

Fishbowl Discussion

The fishbowl discussion is a format that encourages inclusive dialogue and active listening. A small group of participants discuss in an inner circle (the "fishbowl") while the rest of the participants observe from an outer circle. Observers can join the discussion by replacing someone in the fishbowl, allowing for dynamic participation. This method is effective for medium and large groups.

Stakeholder Role-Playing

Stakeholder role-playing involves participants taking on the roles of different stakeholders relevant to a particular issue or project. By simulating these perspectives, participants gain empathy and a deeper understanding of different viewpoints, which can inform strategy development and decision making. This method is suitable for small to medium sized groups.

SWOT Analysis

SWOT analysis is a structured method to help participants evaluate and refine soil health solutions at different stages of the co-creation process. By identifying **s**trengths, **w**eaknesses, **o**pportunities and **t**hreats, stakeholders can evaluate influencing factors, assess potential or tested solutions, refine implementation strategies and anticipate future challenges. This method promotes a balanced discussion by considering both internal and external aspects, supporting informed decision-making and continuous improvement of solutions.

Action Plan Development

Action plan development is a process in which participants outline the steps needed to achieve specific goals or implement solutions. This includes defining tasks, assigning responsibilities, identifying resources, setting timelines and identifying potential risks. Developing an action plan provides a clear roadmap for implementation and accountability.

Focus on Soil Literacy in Co-Creation Sessions

One of the core principles of soil health living labs is the aspect of soil literacy. Soil literacy helps to increasing understanding of soil health among diverse audiences through education and engagement. It helps individuals to

recognise soil's critical role in ecosystem resilience, climate action, and in food security. To implement the soil literacy principle, our project partners from RISE (Hayley Ho, Fanny Lindh, and Alina Östling) created several method modules that can be used in the iCOSHELLS co-creation sessions. These modules are easy to implement and can be used as part of any co-creation session online or in-person:

- **Local Soil:** To sensitise and understand soil as a living entity by characterising soil from a more-than-human perspective through the discussion of values, interactive capabilities, needs and senses.
- **Community Soil:** To explore and discuss from a more-than-human perspective soil as an important stakeholder in the community by creating a Community Soil Manifesto based on the Mission Soil Manifesto.
- **System Soil:** To discuss and think of soil as a stakeholder from a more-than-human systems perspective by touching upon issues of climate justice, historical land-use and power, and indigenous knowledge.
- **Soil Walk:** To sensitise, explore and discuss soil from a more-than-human perspective by taking a guided walk in the local area to encounter soil.

The output from the soil literacy methods in the co-creation session will also inform a pop-up exhibition (material that can be used and displayed in existing events in local network, e.g. schools, festivals).

The details about the modules are in the Appendix: [INTERACTIVE SOIL LITERACY METHODS](#).

The iCOSHELLS Train-of-Trainers Sessions

The Train-of-Trainers programme is a structured capacity-building initiative designed to equip Living Lab leaders with the knowledge, skills, and tools needed to effectively facilitate co-creation processes. By preparing a core group of 'co-creation leaders,' the programme creates a multiplier effect. Trained facilitators guide and empower others in participatory innovation, embedding co-creation methodologies within the iCOSHELLS Living Labs and ensuring long-term impact.

In iCOSHELLS, the Train-of-Trainers programme was structured around three progressive sessions, each building on the previous one to ensure a comprehensive understanding of Living Lab governance, co-creation dynamics, and operational implementation. The programme was guided by the following core principles:

- **Progressive Learning:** A step-by-step approach where each session deepens participants' knowledge and skills.
- **Practical Application:** Emphasis on providing templates, tools, and actionable guidance to support real-world implementation.
- **Tailored Support:** Content adapted to the specific needs and contexts of Living Lab partners, ensuring relevance and flexibility.
- **Empowered Leadership:** Participants are equipped with the skills and confidence to effectively lead co-creation processes in their respective Living Labs.

Through its structured yet adaptable framework, the iCOSHELLS Train-of-Trainers programme empowers Living Lab leaders to foster meaningful collaboration, drive innovation, and create lasting impact in their communities.

This section of the report sums up the Train of Trainer sessions and highlights the programme's structured approach, core principles, and its role in building capacity for co-creation leadership within the iCOSHELLS Living Labs.

Train-of-Trainers Sessions Overview

Figure 4: Concept of Train-of-Trainers sessions.

Session I: Early Planning for Co-Creation

The first Train-of-Trainers session introduces the core principles of Soil Health Living Labs and the concept of co-creation within them (Sec. [Co-Creation in the iCOSHells Living Labs](#)). Participants were guided through the basic elements of successful Living Labs, with a focus on understanding the collaborative and participatory nature of co-creation. This session also included a discussion of the first co-creation session, providing Living Lab partners with practical templates and tools needed for its implementation.

Rationale: The first Train-of-Trainers session was designed to address the need for Living Labs to start planning their co-creation sessions earlier than originally anticipated in the project timeline. This was necessary due to seasonal constraints, which required timely preparation to align activities with agricultural cycles. To support this, we organised bilateral meetings and a dedicated first Train-of-Trainers session to provide Living Labs with the tools and guidance to effectively initiate their co-creation processes.

Session II: Shared Governance Framework and Monitoring & Evaluation

The second Train-of-Trainers session focused on the success factors for Living Labs as defined by ATB (Orzco et al. (2025); see also Subsec. [iCOSHells Monitoring and Evaluation Framework](#)) and explores the operational structure for implementing Living Labs as outlined in Deliverable 2.1. Participants were introduced to the frameworks and methodologies that underpin effective Living Lab governance, including monitoring and evaluation approaches. This session emphasised the importance of key performance indicators (KPIs) and processes for assessing the success of Living Labs, ensuring that partners are equipped to measure and improve their impact.

Rationale: The second Train-of-Trainers session was developed in response to the distributed responsibility for the conceptual development of the Living Lab approach and its governance across different partners within iCOSHells. To ensure coherence and alignment, a joint session was designed to demonstrate how these elements

could be integrated into a unified governance framework. This included discussions on monitoring and evaluation approaches to enable Living Labs to operationalise their activities within a structured and collaborative framework.

Session III: Practical Advice for Co-Creation Based on Partners' Needs

The third Train-of-Trainers session focused on the practical aspects of co-creation within iCOSHELLS Living Labs. Based on the needs and feedback of the Living Lab partners, this session provided detailed guidance on the conceptual framework and practical implementation of co-creation. Participants were supported to adapt the co-creation methodology to their specific context, ensuring that the process is both relevant and effective for the local stakeholders in each Living Lab. Additionally, the tools and templates to support the planning, preparation, of facilitation of co-creation sessions (cf. Subsec. [Planning and Facilitating Co-Creation Sessions](#)) were presented and discussed.

Rationale: The third Train-of-Trainers session was tailored to provide practical advice based on the specific needs and challenges identified by the Living Lab partners. This session focused on practical guidance, troubleshooting and sharing best practice to ensure that Living Labs can effectively implement and scale up their initiatives.

Train-of-Trainers Session I

The first Train of Trainer session took place in January and February 2025, six times in total, with each session tailored to the individual challenges and prior knowledge of the local Living Lab partners. Each session lasted between one and a half to two hours and was conducted by trainers from the CSCP. The sessions consisted of three parts.

- 1. Introduction to the Concept of Mission Soil Living Labs:** In the first part, the concept of Mission Soil Living Labs was introduced to the local Living Lab stakeholders as presented in Subsec. [Soil Health in the European Union](#)) and the Living Lab principles as presented in Subsec. [Guiding Principles for the iCOSHELLS Living Labs](#).
- 2. Introduction to Co-Creation in iCOSHELLS:** In the second part, the concept of co-creation in iCOSHELLS was introduced to the participants (see Subsec. [Co-Creation Process in iCOSHELLS](#)).
- 3. Focus on Specific Living Labs:** The third part of the session focussed on the specific Living Lab and provided insights into its purpose, methods and tools. The status quo was discussed and the current challenges and opportunities in the Living Lab context were outlined. This formed the basis for understanding the specific needs and goals of the co-creation process and for jointly planning the first co-creation session.

Train-of-Trainers Session II

The 2nd Train-of-Trainers session was facilitated by CSCP, ATB, and GAIA and held online on 17 February from 10:30 to 13:00 (CET). The session aimed to improve the operational excellence of iCOSHELLS Living Labs by fostering collaboration, identifying success factors and setting up effective monitoring and evaluation strategies. The target audience included consortium partners involved in the operational set-up and management of Living Labs. A total of 24 people from consortium partners and Living Labs took part.

The session was divided into four key segments:

1. Setting the context: Living Labs in the EU Soil Mission.
2. Success factors for iCOSHELLs Living Labs.
3. iCOSHELLs operational structure for Living Lab implementation.
4. A multi-level approach to data collection in Living Labs.

Part 1: Setting the Context: Living Labs in the EU Soil Mission

This segment, led by the CSCP and LL coordinators, provided a brief summary of the 1st Train-of-Trainers session (see Subsec. [Train-of-Trainers Session I](#)) on the principles of soil health living labs (see Subsec. [Guiding Principles for the iCOSHELLs Living Labs](#)), and the concept of co-creation and its implementation in iCOSHELLs (see Sec. [Co-Creation in the iCOSHELLs Living Labs](#)). Input from the Living Lab coordinators on their first co-creation session was shared.

Part 2: Success Factors for iCOSHELLs Living Labs

In the second session, participants explored the key success factors for Soil Health Living Labs (see Subsec. [Living Lab Governance Success Factors](#)), starting with a presentation by ATB that outlined seven critical factors. An initial evaluation of Living Labs was shared, highlighting strengths and areas for improvement. In breakout sessions, participants reflected on how to refine and adapt these success factors to their specific contexts. They also discussed the weighting of each factor and identified key performance indicators (KPIs) to track progress. The results of these discussions informed [D1.2 \(Determination and parametrization of success factors for LLs\)](#).

Part 3: iCOSHELLs Operational Structure for Living Lab Implementation

In the third part of the session the operational structure of the Living Labs was presented by GAIA. It includes a dedicated Living Lab office for coordination, a steering group to oversee strategic decisions, clearly defined roles and responsibilities to ensure accountability, an experimental management approach for real-world innovation, regular stakeholder engagement to promote co-creation and high-impact solutions, systematic monitoring and reporting to track progress against KPIs., and a continuous feedback system for adaptability and improvement. Further details on the operational structure are presented in [D2.1 \(LL Operational Structure Document\)](#).

Part 4: A Multi-Level Approach to Data Collection in Living Labs

In the concluding part, CSCP addressed the multilevel approach to data in iCOSHELLs, explaining with ATB and GAIA how data is monitored and evaluated in iCOSHELLs (see Subsec. [iCOSHELLs Monitoring and Evaluation Framework](#)). The session concluded with a discussion on data collection and a view to the next Train-of-Trainers session.

Train-of-Trainers Session III

The third Train-of-Trainers session was facilitated by CSCP and RISE and took place online from 13:00 – 15:00 on 26 March, 2025. All Living Labs participated. The session aimed to provide a framework for co-creation in iCOSHells Living Labs and to enable Living Lab partners to develop locally specific co-creation approaches and sessions. The target audience included consortium partners and Living Lab representatives involved in the design and implementation of co-creation activities.

The session was divided into three parts:

1. Developing a Living Lab co-creation plan tailored to the local Living Lab context
2. Developing a co-creation session with tools, templates and discussion groups on selected challenges.
3. Stimulating soil literacy in co-creation sessions, with an approach and recommended activities.

Part 1: How to Develop a Local Living Lab Co-Creation Plan

This session focused on creating a co-creation plan in the iCOSHells Living Labs (see Subsec. [The iCOSHells Co-Creation Process](#)). It consisted of three interconnected sections, beginning with an overview of co-creation requirements. This included an interactive recap of the definition and benefits of co-creation, key Living Lab principles, and relevant soil health stakeholder groups. It was outlined how the eight planned co-creation sessions can support Living Lab activities, emphasising the need to tailor each session to local realities while ensuring alignment with core Living Lab principles. A sample co-creation process provided a concrete example of how these sessions can be strategically integrated. The session then featured a case presentation from the Horizon Europe Project [bioSoilutions](#), illustrating the diversity of co-creation approaches in Living Labs. The case study highlighted the importance of adapting co-creation concepts to local challenges while maintaining a continuous process of learning and refinement. It demonstrated how their approach evolved to meet the specific needs of different Living Labs, offering valuable insights into the flexibility required for successful co-creation. Building on this, participants engaged in an interactive peer learning exercise using a MIRO board, where they analysed Living Lab cases similar to those in iCOSHells. They collaboratively developed co-creation plans, identifying key sessions, relevant stakeholders, and optimal timing for activities. This exercise encouraged participants to apply co-creation principles in practice, fostering collaboration, strategic thinking, and creative problem-solving.

Part 2: How to Develop a Co-Creation Session

This session focused on the practical aspects of planning and running effective co-creation sessions (see Subsec. [The iCOSHells Co-Creation Process](#)). It began with an introduction to a script template and points to consider when preparing co-creation sessions, which provided participants with a structured approach to organising their sessions. Insights were shared on how to effectively complete the template to ensure clarity and purpose in the planning process. An overview of the formalities involved in co-creation sessions was also provided, covering the formalities templates provided in this report. Participants were then introduced to the interactive co-creation methods available to support their work, providing practical resources to improve the design and delivery of co-creation activities. The session included an interactive group exercise using a MIRO board, where participants identified and discussed selected challenges in break-out groups. Key discussion points included recruiting and

incentivising participants, managing time and conflict, and encouraging interaction and engagement in online sessions. Through these discussions, participants developed good practice tips and fostered a collaborative exchange of ideas and strategies to address common challenges.

Part 3: Stimulating Soil Literacy in Co-creation Sessions

This session explored the concept of soil literacy in the context of Mission Soil Living Labs (see Subsec. [Focus on Soil Literacy in Co-Creation Sessions](#)). It introduced a more than human approach to soil literacy, emphasising the interconnectedness of soil with broader ecological and social systems. This perspective encourages participants to see soil not just as a resource, but as a vital, living component of the environment. The session also presented easy-to-apply soil literacy activities that can be integrated into Living Labs and other engagement initiatives, such as pop-up exhibitions. These activities are designed to make soil literacy accessible and engaging to diverse audiences, fostering a deeper understanding and appreciation of soil health. In addition, the meeting included a call for the identification of pilot sites where these soil literacy activities could be tested and refined, to generate practical examples and best practices for integrating soil literacy into co-creation processes, ensuring that soil health remains at the heart of innovative solutions.

Special Train-of-Trainers for the Italian Living Lab

The Italian Living Lab Train-of-Trainers session was held in person on 27 March 2025 from 11:00 to 16:30 at the Faculty of Engineering in Trento. All Italian Living Lab partners participated. This additional session was organised to address the specific needs of the Italian Living Lab's multi-site structure, ensuring that all site leaders had a consistent understanding of iCOSHELLS governance and co-creation approaches. The session revisited and adapted the content of the general sessions to fit the unique context of the Italian Living Lab, providing tailored training for leaders across all sites.

Part 1: Welcome and Introduction

Opening remarks established session objectives and the importance of adapting the iCOSHELLS approach to the Italian Living Lab's unique structure.

Part 2: EU Soil Mission, Living Labs and the iCOSHELLS Approach

This segment provided an overview of the EU Mission for Soil and Living Labs' role in innovation and policy implementation, with emphasis on the iCOSHELLS approach and co-creation methodologies (see Subsec. [Guiding Principles for the iCOSHELLS Living Labs](#)).

Part 3: Developing Co-Creation Timelines for Local Living Labs

Participants worked on developing site-specific co-creation timelines, focusing on strategies for long-term stakeholder engagement. Small groups designed Living Lab concepts tailored to their regional contexts, aligning with [the iCOSHELLS Co-Creation Process](#).

Part 4: Creating Co-Creation Sessions—Practical Implementation

The afternoon session focused on practical co-creation implementation, with participants designing actual co-creation sessions for upcoming Italian Living Lab meetings (see Sec. [Planning and Facilitating Co-Creation Sessions](#)).

Part 5: Monitoring Progress and Evaluating Living Lab Activities

The final segment addressed monitoring frameworks and evaluation tools, providing an overview of the Key Performance Indicators for tracking impact across the diverse Italian sites (see Subsec. [iCOSHELLS Monitoring and Evaluation Framework](#)).

The session concluded with a synthesis of key takeaways and identification of concrete next steps for each site.

iCOSHINE: The iCOSHELLS European Reference Group

Introduction

Another focus of iCOSHELLS is to improve the project results not only within the framework of the co-creation and iterative processes, but also in exchange with other soil stakeholders and projects. This will strengthen the impact and long-term sustainability of the project. To achieve this, iCOSHELLS is developing a European Reference Group (EURG) with the name iCOSHINE (iCOSHELLS Soil Health Information, Networking, and Education). iCOSHINE will be a pan-European platform established to facilitate knowledge sharing, dissemination of best practices and exchange of implementation results between the Living Labs participating in iCOSHELLS. iCOSHINE is composed of selected participants from the Living Labs who will come together to share their experiences, lessons learned, expertise and best practices. Additionally, selected external stakeholders can contribute to iCOSHINE meetings. The group will serve as a validation and reality check point, discussing and ensuring the scalability and transferability of project results and solutions.

iCOSHINE has several objectives, including

- To share knowledge, insights, expertise and best practices from all Living Labs to identify synergies and trade-offs at the laboratory and solution level.
- Adopting a pan-EU and systemic perspective to ensure that project outcomes and solutions are scalable and transferable.
- Validate and provide a reality check on project outcomes and solutions.
- To discuss and ensure the scalability and transferability of project results and solutions.

In order to achieve these objectives, iCOSHINE will engage in various activities, including

1. Co-creation sessions to share knowledge and best practices.
2. Analysis of best and worst practices for maturing and creating self-sustaining Living Labs.
3. Discussion to validate project outcomes for scalability and transferability.
4. Cooperation with other European and global platforms and initiatives.

iCOSHINE will also liaise with other European and global platforms and initiatives, including projects funded under the same theme, to collaborate on outreach activities. These projects will be invited to participate in iCOSHINE activities, including co-organising peer learning sessions.

Concept of iCOSHINE in iCOSHells

At the heart of our project strategy, iCOSHINE is an internal exchange and peer learning body that brings together key project stakeholders to foster collaboration, knowledge sharing and the scalability of project outcomes. Through its implementation, we aim to create a framework for active engagement, meaningful interaction and sustainable impact that lasts throughout the project lifecycle.

Meeting Structure and Frequency

iCOSHINE will convene face-to-face once a year, with a total of four meetings planned over the project duration. These meetings will be strategically aligned with major consortium meetings, and the final project conference to maximise participation and relevance. In addition to these in-person gatherings, three online interactions and meetings will be facilitated annually to maintain continuous collaboration and knowledge sharing among iCOSHells members.

Composition and Participation

iCOSHINE is composed of representatives from the six Living Labs involved in the project. These members will bring their unique perspectives, experiences, and expertise to the group. Additionally, external stakeholders will be invited to participate in online meetings when their involvement aligns with the group's objectives and can contribute to impactful discussions. This inclusive approach ensures that iCOSHINE benefits from diverse insights while maintaining a focused and efficient core group.

Knowledge Exchange and Impact

The first year of iCOSHINE's activities will focus on knowledge exchange, enabling members to share best practices, lessons learned, and innovative solutions. In the following years, the emphasis will shift to impact with the group working to validate and scale the project's outcomes, ensuring their transferability across different contexts and regions.

Collaboration with iCOSHells WP 5, WP 6, and WP7

iCOSHINE collaborates with WP 5, WP 6, and WP 7 to enhance knowledge exchange and align Living Lab insights with broader project goals. WP 5 focuses on replicating and scaling soil health solutions, WP 6 seeks to integrate the iCOSHells Living Labs into sustainable agricultural practices, and WP 7 ensures long-term impact through communication, dissemination, and capacity building. To maximise synergies, CSCP consults with these work packages before setting iCOSHINE meeting agendas, ensuring discussions address both Living Lab needs and project-wide objectives.

Collaboration with Experts and Multipliers

iCOSHINE will actively seek to connect with selected experts and multipliers beyond the project's immediate scope. While the group will maintain its distinct identity and objectives, it will also engage with initiatives like SOILL-Startup (<https://www.soill2030.eu>), or other relevant platforms by inviting their representatives to online meetings

when their expertise can add value. This approach ensures that iCOSHINE remains open to external insights while staying focused on its core mission.

Activities and Outcomes

iCOSHINE will engage in a variety of activities to achieve its objectives, including:

- **Best Practice Sharing:** Facilitating exchange of successful strategies and lessons learned across Living Labs.
- **Impact Validation:** Providing a reality check on project outcomes to ensure their scalability and applicability.
- **Collaborative Outreach:** Partnering with external initiatives to amplify the project's reach and impact.

Sustainability of iCOSHINE

iCOSHINE is designed to facilitate exchange and peer learning throughout the iCOSHells project. Its long-term sustainability will depend on the exploitation strategy and SOIL-L activities. After the project, iCOSHINE could be integrated as a sub-group within SOIL-L or included in the sustainability plans of iCOSHells Living Labs. The final decision on its continuation and structure will be made based on project developments and stakeholder needs.

How iCOSHINE Complements SOIL-L Activities

The exchange within iCOSHINE complements the broader exchange facilitated by SOIL-L (<https://www.soill2030.eu>) across all Mission Soil Living Labs. While SOIL-L provides a broader platform for sharing insights and best practices across different projects, iCOSHINE focuses on the specific challenges, priorities and learnings within the iCOSHells. This project-specific approach allows for tailored discussions, targeted collaboration and strategic selection of topics and participants. The in-depth exchange within iCOSHINE enhances knowledge sharing, promotes synergies and enables direct comparison of approaches, ultimately strengthening the overall quality and impact of co-creation efforts in soil health innovation.

Conclusions and Outlook

The Living Lab Governance Framework in iCOSHELLS has been developed through a collaborative effort among project partners, with key contributions from ATB on success factors (D1.2), GAIA on operational structures and indicators for excellence (D2.1), and CETENMA on soil health monitoring and evaluation (D3.1). This report provides the final piece of the framework by outlining guiding principles for Living Labs, the Living Lab Co-Creation Process, and detailing the different layers of monitoring and evaluation in iCOSHELLS.

A major focus of this report was co-creation, which lies at the core of the Living Lab approach. By involving land users and diverse stakeholders, co-creation enables the joint development, refinement, and adoption of innovative soil health solutions. The report offers hands-on guidance for Living Lab partners on designing effective co-creation processes and employing interactive methods to maximise engagement.

Additionally, the report conceptualised iCOSHINE, the European Reference Group, which fosters collaboration across iCOSHELLS Living Labs and aligns them with broader European soil health initiatives. This platform ensures that project outputs contribute to the wider soil health agenda while remaining adaptable to regional contexts.

All concepts, templates, and methodologies presented in this report were transferred to Living Lab leaders through a Train-of-Trainers programme. The Train-of-Trainers sessions equipped participants with the knowledge to implement governance and co-creation processes, tailor them to their local contexts, and ensure alignment across Living Labs.

Next Steps

In Work Package 1, each Living Lab will conduct eight co-creation sessions, beginning in early 2025 and aligned with local planting seasons. CSCP will continue to support Living Lab leaders in implementing and refining co-creation processes. The outcomes of these sessions will be documented in Co-Creation Session Summary Reports (Deliverables 1.4 – 1.7).

iCOSHINE will be formally established, with its first online session planned for early summer 2025, followed by an in-person session at the iCOSHELLS General Assembly in October 2025. The activities and outcomes of iCOSHINE will be captured in Deliverables 1.8 – 1.11 of Work Package 1, ensuring continuous knowledge exchange and impact assessment throughout the project.

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Appendix

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**TEMPLATE FOR CO-CREATION
SESSION SCRIPTS**

CSCP

Details of co-creation session

Date / Time	
Purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Please list the purposes of your session here
Participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Please list the (groups of) participants here
Location	
Language	
Format	In person / online
Organizer	

Meeting Agenda and Facilitation (including sample text)

Time	Point/Topic – What to discuss?	Method – How to discuss?	Materials – What is needed?	Facilitating roles
XX	1. Welcome and Introductions	Speech/ no special method	-	1. Facilitator 2. Maybe another speaker who welcomes participants
XX	2. iCOSHELLS project	1. Presentation 2. Questions & Answers (Q&A) – Ask participants if they have questions	Meeting presentation	1. Facilitator 2. Time keeper
XX				
XX				
XX	7. Summary and Take Away's	Possibility to note down key take away's on a flipchart (or digitally in the presentation)	Maybe: Flipchart + Marker	1. Facilitator 2. Someone who notes down key take away's

TEMPLATE FOR CO-CREATION
REPORTS

icosHELLS

**TEMPLATE FOR
CO-CREATION
REPORTS**

CSCP

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Summary of the Co-Creation Session

In order to learn from the session and to be able to report on it to the EU, we want you to summarise each co-creation session in a structured format. For, this purpose, please find a structured reports template below. Please refer to the notes and transcriptions of each session as well as participant feedback while feeling in the report.

Session Overview

Purpose	What was the main objective or focus of the session?
Topics	Which topics were discussed during the meeting? List at least 5 topics and/or provide us with the agenda of the session.
Location	When and where did the session take place? Was it in person, online, or hybrid?
Facilitation/Minutes	Who facilitated the session? Who documented the session?
Participants	How many participants attended, and which stakeholder groups were represented? Were there any notable absences or underrepresented groups? How was the diversity of the participants (e.g., in terms of expertise, sectors, or demographics)?
Materials	Were any materials or resources shared with participants before or during the session?
Documentation	What kind of documentation was produced (e.g., minutes, visual maps, recordings)?
Consent form	In which form was the consent form provided, discussed, and signed (physically, digitally)?

Facilitation and Stakeholder Dynamics

Interactions	<p>Were people really engaged? Where they participating? Did you sense some apathy in the participants? Here we want to know how they were feeling during the meeting.</p> <p>Rate the mood considering -5 being not engaged to 5 being engaged.</p>
Facilitation methods	<p>What methods, tools, or approaches were used to facilitate the session (e.g., brainstorming, role-playing, world café)?</p> <p>Were these methods effective in achieving the session’s goals? Why or why not?</p>
Insights for future stakeholder engagement	<p>How can important stakeholder groups who were absent from this session be further engaged in future engagement activities?</p> <p>How can lowly engaged participants be better addressed in future engagement activities?</p> <p>How can high engagement of stakeholders be leveraged to strengthen future engagement activities?</p>
Conflicts	<p>Did any conflicts, tensions, or misunderstandings arise? If so, how were they addressed?</p>

Outcomes and Insights

Outcomes	<p>What was achieved during this session? List at least 5 outcomes of the meeting (e.g., ideas, insights, agreements, action points)?</p> <p>Were there any unexpected findings or challenges that emerged?</p> <p>How do the results contribute to the objectives of the Living Lab as a whole?</p>
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Please provide a brief overview of the action points stemming from the meeting and please indicate, if possible, the deadline and responsible organisation and person for each item. Please add new rows as necessary.

Action point(s)	Followed up by	Until

Reflections and Learnings

Please provide a brief description of the key learnings related to the planning and implementation of the co-creation session: What went well, what needs to be improved for the upcoming meetings etc. Also please reflect on the support that was provided to you and to what extent it was useful to you. Please add new rows as necessary. If you have collected such organisational feedback from participants, please feel free to highlight it in this section.

<p>What went well and will be implemented again in the next session? Think about the place where the session was facilitated, the format, people’s participation, etc.</p>
<p>What needs to be improved? What needs to be modified for next session? Think about the place where the session was facilitated, the format, the homology in people’s participation, etc.</p>
<p>What further support would you need?</p>

<p>Did the methods used during this session (e.g., World café), gave a positive outcome? Should they be kept for next sessions? If not, why?</p>
<p>Other</p>

Checklist of Returning Materials

This is a guiding list indicating all the materials and resources that need to be shared after the conclusion of the co-creation session to complete the reporting process.

Material	Provided	Not provided
Agenda of the session		
Meeting presentation (if there was one)		
Meeting script (if there was one)		
List of Participants		
Consent forms		
Feedback questionnaires		

TEMPLATE FOR CONSENT FORM
CO-CREATION SESSIONS

icosHELLS

**TEMPLATE FOR
CONSENT FORM
FOR CO-
CREATION
SESSIONS**

provided by CSCP

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Consent form

Introduction

Soil degradation is a major challenge that affects the environment, food security, and the economy. It can lead to problems like lower crop production, water pollution, and loss of biodiversity. The iCOSHELLS project, funded by the EU Mission “A Soil Deal for Europe,” is working to address these issues by setting up six Soil Health Living Labs across Europe. These labs aim to create sustainable solutions for soil health that can be used on a larger scale. They focus on involving stakeholders and co-creating solutions that are scientifically sound, locally relevant, and widely accepted.

The [name of Living Lab] Living Lab is one of these six labs. Its goal is to [objective/focus of Living Lab in 1-2 sentences]. As part of this work, at least eight co-creation sessions will be held, using a participatory approach to develop clear and practical insights. The co-creation activities are led by [name of LL lead organisation], and you can learn more about us here: [insert website link].

You are invited to take part in one of our co-creation sessions. This document explains the process and asks for your consent to participate. Please feel free to ask any questions to ensure you fully understand everything. If any terms or information in this document are unclear, ask a project representative to explain them.

Purpose of the Co-Creation Session

The purpose of this session is to [objective/focus of co-creation session in 1 – 2 sentences].

The anonymised results from this session will contribute to developing, testing, and experimenting with solutions in the Living Lab. These results may also be used for project reports, scientific publications, conference presentations, and other project-related outputs.

To support future research, we may store the anonymised data in public databases after the iCOSHELLS project ends. This allows other researchers to use the data for new studies, helping to maximise its impact.

Please find further details on how your data will be collected, protected, and used in the section “Confidentiality, Data Protection and Data Usage” below.

Format of the session

- Duration: xx
- Language: xx
- Facilitator: xx

Confidentiality, Data Protection, and Data Usage

We collect three types of data as part of this co-creation session:

1) Personal data (used only for administrative purposes)

- We collect your name, organisation, and email address **to keep a record of who participated** and to communicate with you about the co-creation activities.
- Personal data may be shared only with the iCOSHELLS project partners, who require this information for administrative and reporting purposes (e.g., for compliance with EU funder requirements).
- Personal data is **stored securely and separately** from the session results. It will **not** be linked to the anonymised data used for our research and innovation activities.
- Your personal data will be kept confidential and will be deleted **no later than 31 January 2034** after the project has been completed and evaluated by the EU. This ensures we comply with the project's reporting requirements and the GDPR.

2) Demographic data (anonymised, used only for statistical purposes)

- We collect **demographic data (such as gender, age group, and other details) anonymously through a confidential survey** during the session. This data is collected solely for statistical purposes and will not be linked to any personal data or used to identify participants.
- Anonymised demographic data, that cannot be linked to your personal identity, may be shared with iCOSHELLS project partners for statistical, research, innovation, reporting, and dissemination purposes.
- We apply the principle of data minimisation, meaning that we only collect the minimum amount of information necessary to achieve the objectives of the project. Your responses are anonymised and will not be used for any other purpose.

3) Data capturing co-creation session results (anonymised, used for research and innovation purposes)

- During the session, we will take notes and document the discussions digitally.
- These records will be **fully anonymised**, meaning they will not include any information that could identify you. The original records will be deleted within within 3 months after the session.
- Anonymised data, that cannot be linked to your personal identity, may be shared with all iCOSHELLS project partners for research, innovation, reporting, and dissemination purposes.
- The anonymised data may be used in project reports, scientific publications, presentations, and other project-related outputs. It may also be stored in public databases after the project ends to support future research. It will be retained indefinitely.

This study complies with the **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (EU) 2016/679** and the **European Commission's Ethics Guidelines for Research**, particularly:

- **GDPR Article 6 – Lawfulness of Processing:**
Your participation is voluntary, and by agreeing to take part, you consent to the collection and processing of anonymised data. We are also required to keep attendance records for reporting obligations to our

funderson, which are stored securely and not linked to the anonymised data. The research is conducted in the public interest, aiming to contribute to sustainable soil health solutions.

- **GDPR Article 7 – Conditions for Consent:**

Your consent to participate is freely given, specific, informed, and unambiguous. You are free to withdraw your consent at any time without the need to provide justification for your decision and without any negative consequences.

We may use **AI tools for transcription and data processing** of anonymised data. If AI tools are used for transcribing or processing data (such as speech-to-text services or automated analysis), we ensure that the data will be processed in **compliance with the EU Artificial Intelligence Act (2021/0106), as well as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)**.

We ensure that:

- **Only anonymised data is used in AI tools.**
- AI transcription tools do not store or link personal data.
- The use of AI tools for transcription will adhere to transparency and fairness principles, in line with applicable EU regulations.

Rights of Participants

- Your participation in the session is voluntary. You have the right not to answer any question, and to stop your participation at any time and for any reason.
- You have the right to access, correct, or delete your data at any time. To request the access, correction, or deletion of your personal data, please contact the “contact person” specified below.
- You can withdraw your consent to use the data without any negative consequences. Any personal data collected up until the point of withdrawal will be deleted, unless there is a legal obligation to retain it.
- You have the right to lodge a complaint with a data supervisory authority. A full list of the country specific data supervisory authorities can be found [here](#).

Contact information

For any questions or concerns, please contact

Contact person: [please specify contact person for the co-creation session here and provide their email address]

Data Protection Officer: [please specify data protection officer of your organisation here and provide their email address]

Project Coordinating Team iCOSHELLS:

Erik Sindhoj: erik.sindhoj@ri.se; Cheryl Cordeiro: cheryl.marie.cordeiro ; Mar Basterrechea: mbasterrechea@zabala.es ; Mikel Lorea: mlorea@zabala.es; Raquel Maeztu: rmaeztu@zabala.es

Participant Consent

Please carefully read and sign this consent form. It allows us to use the information that you share with us during the co-creation session research and innovation purposes.

- I voluntarily agree to participate in this co-creation session, which is part of the iCOSHells project. I am 18 years or older and competent to provide consent.
- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason.
- I have had the purpose and nature of the project and the co-creation session explained to me in writing and I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the project and the session.
- I understand that in any publication on the results of this research my identity will remain anonymous.
- I have read and understood the "Confidentiality and Data Protection" section of this form, and I agree to the use of my data as outlined there. I had the opportunity to ask questions about the section.
- I agree to being audio-recorded/ AI-transcribed during the co-creation session. (@LL Leaders: Please specify what applies to your session)
- I agree that photos and videos are taken during the session and that these can be used for iCOSHells publications and communication activities. *(Please cross out if you do not agree with photos and/or videos).*

I have received a copy of this agreement. This consent form is made pursuant to the relevant national, European data protection laws and regulations and personal data treatment obligations.

Date & Location

Name

Signature

TEMPLATE FOR CO-CREATION
PARTICIPANTS SURVEY

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TEMPLATE FOR CO-
CREATION
PARTICIPANTS LIST

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List of Participants

Name of Living Lab:

Date of the Co-Creation Session:

	Name	Signature
1		
2		
3		
4		
5		
6		
7		
8		
9		
10		
11		
12		
13		

	Name	Signature
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TEMPLATE FOR CO-CREATION
PARTICIPANTS SURVEY

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TEMPLATE FOR CO-
CREATION
PARTICIPANTS
SURVEY

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Survey for Participants

This anonymous survey is designed to gather demographic information on participants needed for monitoring and reporting purposes. The data collected will remain confidential and will not be linked to any personal identities.

Question 1: Which stakeholder group do you belong to? (please diversify the groups)

- Land Users and Managers
(e.g., farmers, foresters, landowners, agricultural advisors, urban planners)
- Academics and Researchers
(e.g., university faculty, researchers, soil scientists)
- Industry Representatives
(e.g., businesses, manufacturers, technology providers, agribusiness professionals)
- Policy Makers and Public Sector Bodies
(e.g., government officials, local authorities, policy advisors, environmental agencies)
- Citizens and Community Representatives
(e.g., local residents, community organizers, environmental NGOs)

Question 2: Which age group do you belong to?

- 18-34 years
- 35 - 54 years
- 55 - 69 years
- 70+ years

Question 3: Which gender do you consider yourself?

- Male
- Female
- Non-binary / Third gender
- Prefer not to say

@Living Lab leaders: Please feel free to add any additional demographic questions you believe are relevant for your Living Lab. However, please ensure the questions remain broad and non-specific to protect the anonymity of participants.

TEMPLATE FOR CO-CREATION
FEEDBACK QUESTIONNAIRE

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TEMPLATE FOR
CO-CREATION
FEEDBACK
QUESTIONNAIRE

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Feedback Questionnaire

@Living Lab Leaders: Please adapt the listed questions to the setting and framework of your individual co-creation session and feel free to add any other questions that you find relevant.

- **Make sure to mainly use the rating questions and only include 2 or 3 open answer questions.** Please format the open answer questions, so that participants have sufficient space to answer.
- This questionnaire can either be made available to participants in paper or transferred to an online format (i.e., survey monkey, Google forms).

General information

Have you attended previous meetings in the Living Lab?

Yes

No

SECTION 1: OBJECTIVES AND AGENDA

How useful did you find the co-creation session overall for the Living Lab?

Not at all

Slightly

Moderately

Very

Extremely

How useful did you find the co-creation session overall for your own work?

Not at all

Slightly

Moderately

Very

Extremel

Were the objectives of the co-creation session clear?

Not at all

Slightly

Moderately

Very

Fully

Were the objectives of the co-creation session achieved?

Not at all

Slightly

Partially

Very

Fully

Was the agenda of the co-creation session clear?

Yes

No

SECTION 2: LOCATION AND LENGTH OF THE SESSION

How satisfied were you with the location / the used online platform?

Not at all

Slightly

Moderately

Very

Extremely

If you were unsatisfied, please briefly explain below:

How adequate was the lengths of the co-creation session?

Too short

Fine

Too long

SECTION 3: CONTENT, METHODS AND PARTICIPATION

How interesting did you find the topic of the co-creation session?

<input type="checkbox"/>				
Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely

How did you find the number of participants in the session?

<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Too few	Fine	Too many

Did you have the opportunity to actively participate/share your opinions during the session?

<input type="checkbox"/>				
Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely

Were the facilitation methods used during the session useful and understandable?

<input type="checkbox"/>				
Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely

Did you feel comfortable participating in this session?

<input type="checkbox"/>				
Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely

SECTION 4: INTERACTIONS

Did you get to exchange information with other stakeholders in the session?

<input type="checkbox"/>				
Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely

Did you get to exchange information with the Living Lab organisers?

<input type="checkbox"/>				
Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely

Do you feel well informed by the Living Lab organisers about their current work in the Lab?

<input type="checkbox"/>				
Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely

If you found the level of information exchange insufficient, please briefly explain why and what you would like to see done differently for the next co-creation session?

SECTION 5: OPEN ANSWER QUESTIONS (@Living Lab Leaders: please select the most relevant for you)

What other topics do you feel should have been discussed in the co-creation session?

Do you have any suggestions for improving the co-creation session?

What did you like most about the co-creation session?

Was there any information concerning the co-creation session that was difficult for you to understand?

Do you have any other feedback you would like to give?

Please cite the 3 most valuable pieces of information that you have gained during this co-creation session:

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INTERACTIVE CO- CREATION METHODS

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Brainstorming & Affinity Mapping

Brainstorming is a creative technique designed to generate a wide range of ideas on a specific topic within a short period. Participants are encouraged to think freely and suggest ideas without immediate evaluation or criticism, fostering an open and inclusive environment. This method is effective for both small and larger groups.

Following brainstorming, Affinity Mapping (also known as Affinity Diagramming) is employed to organise the generated ideas. Participants group similar ideas into clusters based on their natural relationships, which helps in diagnosing complex situations and identifying common themes. This structured approach aids in making sense of extensive data and is particularly useful for larger groups.

Overview

Element	Details
General Objective	To generate a diverse set of ideas in an open and inclusive environment and systematically organise them into meaningful clusters, enabling participants to identify patterns, common themes, and key insights.
Sample Objective in iCOSHells	Brainstorming to gather insights from farmers and other stakeholders on their preferred ways of involvement and contributions to the LL. Affinity mapping to categorise and structure these inputs and to align them with the LL context.
Time Needed	30 – 70 min (flexible based on group size and level of detail).
Number of Participants	4 – 50 people; split people in groups of 4-6 per flip chart/ pin board/ virtual break out session.
Materials	Sticky notes (various colours), large flipcharts/ pin boards/ virtual pin boards like MIRO/MURAL etc., markers, printed project goals for reference, tape or board for clustering insights, stickers for optional prioritization.
Moderators	1-2 facilitators to guide discussions, encourage participation, and help with clustering ideas.

Step-by-Step Implementation

1. Introduction & Context Setting (5-10 min)

- Briefly introduce the objective of the session:
“Today, we want to hear directly from you – [participants] – about how you see your role in the Living Labs. Your input will help shape how we work together.”
- Provide a quick refresher on the project goals and previously discussed insights to set the stage.
- Explain the method:
 - We’ll start with an open brainstorming session.
 - Then, we’ll group similar ideas together to identify key themes (Affinity Mapping).
 - Finally, we’ll discuss and refine the ideas collectively.

2. Individual & Group Brainstorming (10-20 min)

- Give each participant sticky notes and markers.
- Ask them to write down their thoughts individually (one idea per sticky note) in response to these questions:
 1. *How would you like to be involved in the Living Labs?*
 2. *What specific skills, resources, or expertise can you contribute?*
(note: you can specify this question if specific contributions are needed)
- 5 minutes before the group work ends, participants share their ideas within their small groups (4-6 people).
- Groups place all their sticky notes on a shared flipchart or board for visibility.

3. Affinity Mapping – Organising Ideas (5-10 min)

- Facilitators help the groups cluster similar ideas together into broad themes (e.g., knowledge sharing, practical fieldwork, policy engagement, funding needs).
- Label each group of ideas with a category title that reflects the main theme.
- If needed, ask participants to help refine or merge overlapping ideas.

4. Group Discussion & Refinement (10-20 min)

- Once the themes are clear, open the floor for discussion:
 1. *Do these categories make sense?*
 2. *Are there any missing perspectives?*
 3. *What seems most important or feasible?*
- Optional: Use dot voting (each participant gets a few stickers to place on the themes they consider most relevant or urgent).
- Facilitators document key insights to ensure they are considered in the next steps of the project.

5. Closing & Linking to Next Steps (5-10 min)

- Summarise the main themes and priorities identified.
- Explain how these insights will be used to structure the Action Plan session.
- Thank participants and encourage them to stay engaged in the next phases of the project.

Dot Voting

Dot Voting, also known as "multi-voting" or "dotmocracy," is a facilitation method used to prioritise options or make collective decisions. Participants are given a set number of stickers or dots and place them next to the options they prefer. The options with the most dots are considered the group's priorities. This technique is simple, transparent, and effective for both small and large groups.

Overview

Element	Details
Objective (general)	To help participants quickly prioritise solutions or ideas by voting with dots, ensuring democratic decision-making.
Sample Objective in iCOSHELLS	To prioritise the solutions that ought to be tested in the LL. Solutions can have been previously developed in co-creation, discussed in a World Café format, or suggested by LL partners.
Time Needed	15 – 30 minutes (depending on the number of options and participants).
Number of Participants	unlimited
Materials	Sticky dots (or markers for manual voting), flipcharts or posters with ideas listed, tape or board for displaying options. Can also be virtual dots on a shared PowerPoint/MIRO/MURAL in virtual co-creation sessions.
Moderators	1 – 2 facilitators to explain the process, ensure clarity of options, and count votes.

Step-by-Step Implementation

1. Introduction & Instructions (3 – 10 min)

- Introduce the purpose of the voting:
“We will now prioritise the solutions or ideas that resonate most with the group, helping us focus on what’s most important moving forward.”
- Explain the dot voting process:
 - Each participant gets a set number of dots (e.g., 3-5 per person).
 - They place their dots on the ideas they find most relevant or important.
 - They can put multiple dots on one idea if they feel strongly about it.
 - The idea(s) with the most dots will be prioritised for further discussion or action.

2. Voting Process (7 – 15 min)

- Participants move around and place their dots on the listed ideas.
- Facilitators monitor the process, ensuring everyone participates and understands the system.

3. Review & Next Steps (5 min)

- Facilitators count the dots and highlight the top-voted ideas.
- Explain how these results will inform the next workshop steps.
- Thank participants for their input before transitioning to the next activity.

Conversation Starters

Conversation Starters are prompts or questions designed to initiate dialogue on specific topics. They serve to spark discussion, encourage participants to share perspectives, and delve deeper into subjects. This method is versatile and can be adapted for both small and large groups, depending on the context and objectives.

Overview

Element	Details
Objective (general)	To initiate meaningful discussions and encourage participants to share perspectives by using prompts that spark dialogue and deepen engagement with the topic.
Sample Objective in iCOSHELLS	To spark open conversations on key aspects of the LLs, encouraging participants to share their thoughts and experiences without the pressure of reaching conclusions. Facilitators take notes to capture key discussion points.
Time Needed	15 – 45 minutes (depending on the number of questions discussed).
Number of Participants	4 – 24 people; ideally 8-16 participants in total, or groups of 6-8 people.
Materials	(Printed) conversation starter cards, a timer for rotations, and notebooks or digital tools for facilitators to take notes.
Moderators	1 – 3 facilitators to introduce the method, monitor discussions, and take notes.

Step-by-Step Implementation

1. Introduction & Context Setting (3 min)

- Introduce the purpose of the session:
“This session is all about sparking conversation on [e.g. the planned experiments in the Living Labs]. There are no right or wrong answers—just an opportunity to exchange ideas and perspectives.”
- Explain the method:
 - Facilitator asks thought-provoking questions (prompts) tailored to the goals of the session and shows them to participants (e.g., on a slide or a printed card).
 - Participants note down their thoughts on the question.
 - After everybody had time to think about the question, participants share their thoughts.
 - There is no need to reach a conclusion—just engage in conversation. All thoughts are welcome.
 - Facilitators will take notes on key discussion points (in each group).
 - Once the time is up, a new thought-provoking question (prompt) is discussed.
- *Alternative: Participants can also be split up in smaller groups and each group discusses one question which is provided to them as a print-out. After each group discussion, groups can rotate to discuss other questions.*

2. Discussion of conversation starter questions (approx. 7 min per question)

- Setup: (Printed) conversation starter questions are asked to participants *(either one question after another to the whole group; or different questions to different groups of participants).*
- Examples for conversation starter questions:
 - What do you think is the most important goal of a Living Lab?
 - We are thinking of implementing [describe solution/experiment]. What opportunities [or challenges, risks] do you associate with this?
 - What changes have you observed in soil quality over the years?
- Process:
 - A question is discussed for 5-10 minutes.
 - Facilitators take notes on emerging themes, interesting perspectives, or points of debate.
 - A facilitator signals when time is up.
 - The next question is discussed for 5-10 minutes, notes are taken and the facilitator signals time is up.
 - Continue this process until all questions have been discussed.
 - *If participants were split up into groups: Groups rotate to a new table after the discussion of each question and engage with a new question.*

3. Wrap-Up (5 min, optional)

- Once all questions have been discussed, the facilitator thanks participants and briefly acknowledges the richness of the discussions.
- Facilitators ensure that the notes collected will be available for later reference in the workshop.
- The session transitions into the next activity without a formal summary.

World Café

The World Café is a structured conversational process intended to facilitate open and intimate discussions, and link ideas within a larger group to access the collective intelligence. Participants split into smaller groups and discuss a topic at several tables, with individuals switching tables periodically and introducing their previous discussion to the new table. This method is particularly effective for larger groups (more than 15 people) and aims to improve large-group discussion through informal café-style conversations.

Overview

Element	Details
Objective (general)	To facilitate a structured in-depth discussion on key topics by rotating participants across different tables, ensuring diverse perspectives and knowledge exchange. Table facilitators take notes to capture key insights.
Sample Objective in iCOSHELLS	To facilitate in-depth discussions on potential solutions that can be tested in the LL by assigning each table a specific solution, allowing participants to explore its feasibility, benefits, and implementation strategies through rotating conversations and collective knowledge exchange.
Time Needed	45 – 120 mins (depending on the number of tables and depth of discussion).
Number of Participants	15 – 50 people, ideally in small groups of 5-8 per table.
Materials	Large sheets of paper/ flip charts/ pin boards (one for each table), markers, sticky notes, printed guiding questions, timer for rotations. Can also be virtual pin boards like MIRO/MURAL etc. in virtual co-creation sessions.
Moderators	1 facilitator to introduce the method and monitor the discussions. Each table also has a table host (either a participant or a moderator) who stays to guide new arrivals.

Step-by-Step Implementation

1. Introduction & Context Setting (5-10 min)

- Introduce the purpose of the session:
“In this session, we will have rotating discussions on key topics related to [e.g. possible solutions to be tested in our LL]. You will contribute your perspectives and build upon the ideas of others.”
- Explain the process:
 - There are different tables, each with a specific topic/question.
 - Participants rotate between tables, engaging in multiple discussions.
 - A table host remains at each table to facilitate table discussions and to summarise previous discussions for newcomers.
 - Facilitators will take notes on key insights emerging across tables.
Alternative: Participants document discussion results on discussion paper/ flipchart/ pin board.

2. Discussion Rounds (3 – 4 rounds of 10 – 20 min each; 30 – 90 min total)

- Round 1: Each group sits at a table and starts discussing the assigned topic, using the large sheet of paper/ flipchart/ pin board to capture key ideas.
- Rotation: After the time is up, participants move to a new table (except for the table host). The host briefly summarises the previous discussion before the new round begins.
- Repeating the process: Each group builds on the conversation from previous participants, deepening the discussion.
- Main facilitator moves around to observe and take notes on recurring themes.

3. Summary of Results (10 – 20 min)

- After the last rotation, table hosts sum up the ideas discussed at their table.
 - What common themes emerged?
 - Were there any surprising insights?
 - What ideas feel the most relevant or actionable?
- The session transitions into the next workshop activity.

Fishbowl Discussion

The Fishbowl Discussion is a format that promotes inclusive dialogue and active listening. A small group of participants engages in a discussion in an inner circle (the "fishbowl"), while the remaining participants observe from an outer circle. Observers can join the discussion by replacing someone in the fishbowl, allowing for dynamic participation. This method is effective for medium-sized and large groups and encourages deep, focused conversations.

Overview

Element	Details
Objective (general)	To foster inclusive and dynamic discussions by allowing participants to engage in a focused conversation while others observe and listen, promoting active reflection, diverse input, and deeper exploration of key topics.
Sample Objective in iCOSHELLS	To critically assess and refine tested soil health solutions by facilitating a structured discussion where key stakeholders share their experiences in the inner circle, while others listen, reflect, and contribute new insights, ensuring the solutions are adapted for greater feasibility and impact.
Time Needed	45 – 60 minutes
Number of Participants	15 – 40 people (5-8 active participants at a time, others observing)
Materials	5 – 8 chairs arranged in an inner circle (for speakers) and outer circle (for observers), a guiding question, and a timer
Moderators	1 – 2 facilitators to introduce the topic, ensure smooth transitions, and capture key insights

Step-by-Step Implementation

1. Introduction & Setup (5-10 min)

- The facilitator explains the purpose of the Fishbowl:
“This method allows for focused discussion while encouraging active listening. A small group will discuss and evaluate [e.g. the results of the first round of experiments in our LL] while others observe. Observers can join the conversation by swapping places.”
- Arrange seating:
 - The inner circle (5-8 seats) is for active discussants.
 - The outer circle is for observers who listen and take notes.
- Introduce the discussion prompt (e.g.: Based on the solutions tested so far, what have been the key successes and challenges in implementation? How can we adjust or improve these solutions to enhance their effectiveness, scalability, and adoption?).

2. Fishbowl Discussion (30-40 min)

- First Round (10-20 min):
 - Inner circle participants discuss the topic.
 - Outer circle listens, taking notes on key points.
- Swapping Participants (10-20 min):
 - Observers can tap a participant on the shoulder to swap seats and join the discussion.
 - The conversation continues with fresh perspectives.

3. Reflection & Wrap-Up (approx. 10 min)

- The facilitator asks e.g.,
 - What were the most compelling points raised?
 - Did any perspectives change through listening?
 - What should we take forward from this discussion?
- Facilitators summarise insights before moving to the next session.

Stakeholder Role-Playing

Stakeholder Role-Playing involves participants adopting the roles of various stakeholders relevant to a particular issue or project. By simulating these perspectives, participants gain empathy and a deeper understanding of different viewpoints, which can inform strategy development and decision-making. This method is suitable for small to medium-sized groups, depending on the number of stakeholder roles identified.

Overview

Element	Details
Objective	To enhance empathy and refine strategies by having participants take on different stakeholder roles (e.g., farmers, policymakers, researchers) and discuss soil health solutions from their assigned perspective.
Sample Objective in iCOSHells	To explore the feasibility and impact of soil health solutions by having participants role-play key stakeholders, enabling them to identify potential conflicts, synergies, and implementation ideas from multiple perspectives.
Time Needed	60 – 90 minutes
Number of Participants	15 – 36 people, working in small groups of 3-6.
Materials	Role description cards, scenario sheets, flipcharts, markers, and optional props to represent roles. Can also be done virtually (groups prepare in virtual break-out rooms and share their perspectives in main room).
Moderators	1 – 2 facilitators to provide support to group preparations and role plays

Step-by-Step Implementation

1. Introduction & Setup (10 min)

- Welcome participants and introduce the goal:
“Today, you will step into the shoes of different stakeholders involved in soil health. By discussing solutions from their perspectives, we can identify challenges, opportunities, and points of collaboration.”
- Explain the process:
 - Each group will receive a role card describing a stakeholder (e.g., farmer, researcher, policymaker, agronomist, environmental activist).
 - A scenario sheet presents a soil health solution to discuss from their assigned perspective.

2. Role-Playing Discussions (40-60 min)

- Group Discussions (20-30 min):
 - Participants stay in character and discuss how their stakeholder would view the problem, the challenges they face, and what solutions they support.
 - They note key points on flipcharts.
 - Facilitators move between groups, prompting deeper reflections.
- Group Sharing (approx. 5 min per group; in total 20-30 min):
 - Each group presents their stakeholder’s position.
 - Facilitators highlight patterns, differences, and surprising insights.

3. Reflection & Wrap-Up (10-15 min)

- The facilitator asks e.g.,
 - What perspectives were most surprising?
 - Where were the biggest conflicts or areas of alignment?
 - How can we use this understanding to improve the solution to be tested in the LL?
- Key takeaways are summarised before transitioning to the next session.

SWOT Analysis

SWOT Analysis is a structured method that helps participants assess and refine soil health solutions at different stages of the co-creation process. By identifying Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats, stakeholders can evaluate influencing factors, assess potential or tested solutions, refine implementation strategies, and anticipate future challenges. This method promotes a balanced discussion by considering both internal and external aspects, supporting informed decision-making and the continuous improvement of solutions. This method is effective for small and medium-sized groups.

Overview

Element	Details
Objective (general)	To support the development and refinement of solutions by systematically assessing their strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats, enabling stakeholders to make informed decisions, improve strategies, and enhance the long-term impact of the initiative.
Sample Objective in iCOSHells	To evaluate a soil health solution tested in the LL by identifying its Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats, providing a structured foundation for decision-making.
Time Needed	60 – 90 minutes
Number of Participants	6 – 20 people, working in small groups of 5 – 6
Materials	Large SWOT matrix sheets, markers, sticky notes, and printed prompts to guide analysis. Can also be done virtually (groups prepare in virtual break-out rooms on a virtual pin board with a SWOT matrix and share their results in main room).
Moderators	1 – 2 facilitators to introduce the method, guide discussions, and help refine insights

Step-by-Step Implementation

1. Introduction & Set-up (10 min)

- The facilitator introduces the goal:
“We will systematically analyse a soil health solution, identifying its strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. This will help us to further refine it in the Living Lab.”
- Explain the SWOT framework:
 - Strengths – *What are the internal advantages or positive aspects of this solution that contribute to its success or effectiveness?*
 - Weaknesses – *What limitations, challenges, or areas for improvement exist within this solution?*
 - Opportunities – *What external factors, trends, or conditions could enhance the success or impact of this solution?*
 - Threats – *What external risks, obstacles, or barriers could hinder the success or implementation of this solution?*
- Divide participants into small teams, each working on a specific soil health solution.

2. SWOT Analysis in Teams (40 – 50 min)

- Step 1: Brainstorming (20 – 30 min)
 - Teams write down their ideas for each category using sticky notes and placing them in the SWOT matrix.
 - Facilitators move around, prompting deeper analysis.
- Step 2: Refining & Prioritising (15 – 20 min)
 - Each team clusters their points into key themes per SWOT matrix field
 - They highlight the most critical insights in each category (key strengths, key weaknesses, key opportunities, key challenges).

3. Sharing & Discussion (15 – 20 min)

- Each team presents their SWOT matrix to the larger group.
- Facilitators help connect common insights across teams.
- The discussion focuses on:
 - How can we leverage strengths and opportunities?
 - How can we mitigate weaknesses and threats?
- Facilitators summarise key takeaways before transitioning to the next session.

SWOT Matrix Template

Strengths What are the internal advantages of this solution?	Weaknesses What limitations/ challenges exist within the solution?
Opportunities What external factors could enhance success?	Threats What external risks or barriers could hinder success?

Action Plan Development

Action Plan Development is a process where participants outline the steps necessary to achieve specific goals or implement solutions. This involves defining tasks that need to be done to reach an objective, assigning responsibilities for implementing the tasks, determining required resources, setting timelines, and identifying potential risks. Developing an action plan provides a clear roadmap for execution and accountability. This method can be used by groups of different sizes.

Overview

Element	Details
Objective (general)	To create a clear and actionable roadmap by outlining the necessary steps, responsibilities, resources, and timelines to implement and achieve specific soil health solutions, ensuring accountability and effective execution.
Sample Objective in iCOSHELLS	To develop a detailed action plan for refining and implementing a selected soil health solution by identifying key tasks, assigning responsibilities, setting deadlines, and addressing potential risks, ensuring that all stakeholders are aligned and prepared for successful execution.
Time Needed	2 – 3 hours (adjustable based on depth of discussion; can be shortened by focusing solely on selected aspects of the action plan).
Number of Participants	6 – 24 people; larger groups to be split up in mixed stakeholder sub-groups (4 – 6 per sub-group).
Materials	Printed Action Plan Templates, markers, sticky notes (various colours). Can also be done virtually on a virtual pin board with an Action Plan Template.
Moderators	2 facilitators to guide discussions

Step-by-Step Implementation

1. Introduction & Linking to Previous Activities (15-20 min)

- Recap Key Insights: Briefly summarise the outcomes of previous activities that inform the action plan. Highlight key decisions already made (e.g., the chosen solution, identified challenges, stakeholder insights).
- Set the Context: Explain that this session will focus on defining who does what next to bring the solution to life in real-world testing and scaling.
- Specify following aspects of the action plan template (please see template below)
 - Focus area, Objectives, and Measurable Targets
 - Timeline and Coordinator
- Clarify Expected Outcomes: By the end of this session, participants should have a draft action plan outlining key actions/tasks, responsibilities, resource needs, timelines, and risks.
- *With bigger groups/ limited time, it is recommended to only discuss selected aspects of the action plan, e.g.,*
 - only define actions and risks in one session, and responsibilities and timelines afterwards
 - suggest actions before the session and discuss and further refine them in the session

2. Brainstorming Actions (20 – 30 min)

- Brainstorm the actions/tasks/steps that ought to be included in the action plan with participants? (What needs to be done to reach the objective? Step-by-step)
- Cluster actions into the action plan template.

3. Detail Actions in smaller groups (30 – 45 min)

- Split participants into groups of 4 – 6 people and assign each group with different actions.
- Ask groups to further define each action within the action plan template
 - Who wants to / should be responsible for implementing the action?
 - Who wants to / should support implementing the action?
 - Which personnel, financial, material, and knowledge resources are needed?
 - When can the implementation start? When should it end?
 - What might hinder it? How can these risks be reduced?
- Recording Responses: Groups write into the action plan template.

4. Collate Answers (15 min)

- Facilitators collate the work of the different groups into one large action plan template
- Participants enjoy a break

5. Presenting and Refining Commitments (30 – 45 min)

- Group presentations: Each group shares their actions and how they detailed them.
- Feedback & Alignment: Facilitators and participants discuss overlaps, dependencies, and feasibility. Adjustments are made where needed.

- Refinement of responsibilities: Facilitators and participants discuss responsible and supporting roles and jointly fix them.

6. Finalising Commitments & Next Steps (10 – 30 min)

- Facilitators summarise discussed commitments
- Pledge Wall Activity: Participants write their specific commitment and sign their name to create a sense of accountability.
- Closing Remarks: Facilitators outline follow-up steps, and reinforce the collaborative effort required to achieve success.

Action Plan Template

Focus Area	<i>Briefly describe the specific aspect of the project this action plan addresses (e.g., field testing, stakeholder engagement, policy integration, resource mobilization).</i>
Objectives	<i>Define the objectives of the action plan (e.g., Implementing first iteration of field experiments; Increasing soil literacy among citizens)</i>
Measurable Targets	<i>Define measurable targets to quantify these objectives (e.g., 100 seeds planted, xx plants grown)</i>
Timeline	<i>Specify the overall timeline of the action plan</i>
Coordinator	<i>Specify the organizations responsible for coordinating that the action plan is executed</i>
Involved	<i>Specify the organizations involved in executing the action plan</i>

List the main steps needed to implement the solution, along with who is responsible for each:

No.	Action	Responsible	Supporting	Resources Needed	Timeline	Risks and Mitigation
	<i>Which steps need to be implemented to reach the objective?</i>	<i>Who is responsible for implementing this?</i>	<i>Who supports the implementation?</i>	<i>Which personnel, financial, material, and knowledge resources are needed?</i>	<i>When can the implementation start? When should it end?</i>	<i>What might hinder it? How can these risks be reduced?</i>
1						
2						
3						
4						

(Add more rows as needed)

INTERACTIVE SOIL
LITERACY METHODS

icosHELLs

INTERACTIVE SOIL LITERACY METHODS

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Local Soil

Overview

Element	Details
Objective	To sensitise and understand soil as a living entity by characterising soil from a more-than-human perspective through the discussion of values, interactive capabilities, needs and senses.
Time Needed	30 minutes
Number of Participants	10 – 25 participants, working in smaller groups of approximately 3 people. <i>We encourage a mixed group of stakeholders and to include social stakeholders</i>
Materials	In person: Local soil templates, local soil, pens, tables, post-its Online version: Miro board with Community soil templates
Moderators	1 facilitator to introduce the material, arrange the smaller groups, guide the final entire group discussion

Step-by-Step Implementation

1. Introduction & Context Setting (2 min)

- Briefly introduce the objective of the session:
“Today, we will sensitise and understand soil as a living entity by characterising soil from a more-than-human perspective through the discussion of values, interactive capabilities, needs and senses..”
- Explain that we will work through the Local Soil Template, and hand them out

2. Group work: Local Soil Template (20 mins)

- Divide into groups of approximately 3 people
- Each group gets a Local Soil Template to work on

3. Reflection & Wrap-Up (8 min)

- Put up all the Soil Templates next to each other.
- Facilitator asks participants to reflect on one learning from the activity and write it onto a post-it note.
- Facilitator asks if a few people want to share (if time), summarises activity and wraps up thoughts & learnings.

Community Soil

Overview

Element	Details
Objective	To explore and discuss from a more-than-human perspective soil as an important stakeholder in the community by creating a <i>Community Soil Manifesto</i> based on the <i>Misson Soil Manifesto</i> .
Time Needed	30 minutes
Number of Participants	10 – 25 participants, part of session will involve working in 5 small groups <i>We encourage a mixed group of stakeholders and to include social stakeholders</i>
Materials	In person: Community soil templates, Soil Manifesto template, pens, room arranged with 5 tables for the groups Online version: Miro board with Community soil templates and Soil Manifesto template
Moderators	1 facilitator to introduce the material, arrange the smaller groups for discussion, to guide the final discussion with the entire group to summarise into a group manifesto.

Step-by-Step Implementation

1. Introduction & Context Setting (2 min)

- Briefly introduce the objective of the session:
“To explore and discuss from a more-than-human perspective soil as an important stakeholder in the community by creating a Community Soil Manifesto based on the Misson Soil Manifesto.”
- Explain that we will work through the Community Soil Template, and hand them out

2. Group work: Community Soil Template (12 mins)

- Divide all participants into 5 small groups
- Each group gets their own Community Soil Template to work on (Each group gets a different template with a different question to work on)

3. Reflection & Wrap-Up (10min)

- Each group shares their “summary” point from their template
- Facilitator guides the final discussion with entire group to summarise into the Soil manifesto template.

Systems Soil

Overview

Element	Details
Objective	To discuss and think of soil as a stakeholder from a more-than-human systems perspective by touching upon issues of climate justice, historical land-use and power, and indigenous knowledge
Time Needed	30 minutes
Number of Participants	10 – 30 participants working in smaller groups around 5 people <i>We encourage a mixed group of stakeholders and to include social stakeholders</i>
Materials	In person: Screen to show video material, pens, post-its Online version: To be able to share the video
Moderators	1 facilitator to screen the video, arrange the smaller groups for discussion, to guide the final entire group discussion

Step-by-Step Implementation

1. Introduction & Context Setting (15 min)

- Briefly introduce the objective of the session:
“To discuss and think of soil as a stakeholder from a more-than-human systems perspective by touching upon issues of climate justice, historical land-use and power, and indigenous knowledge”
- Watch the video
- Individual reflections on post-its about what they just saw, think about one thing they would like to share.

2. Group work: Discussion (10 mins)

- Divide all participants groups of around 5 people
- Go around the group to share one reflection
- Group discussion

3. Reflection & Wrap-Up (5min)

- Facilitator asks if a few people want to share (if time), summarises activity and wraps up thoughts & learnings.

Soil Walk

Overview

Element	Details
Objective	To sensitise, explore and discuss soil from a more-than-human perspective by taking a walk in the local area to encounter soil.
Time Needed	60 minutes
Number of Participants	3 – 10 participants <i>We encourage a mixed group of stakeholders and to include social stakeholders</i>
Materials	In person: Facilitator instructions
Moderators	1 facilitator to guide the walk and guide the discussions

Step-by-Step Implementation

Facilitator will have to make pre-preparations for the walk beforehand using the facilitators instructions as a guide.

1. Introduction & Context Setting (2 min)

- Briefly introduce the objective of the session:
“To sensitise, explore and discuss soil from a more-than-human perspective by taking a walk in the local area to encounter soil.”

2. Group walk (50 mins)

- Facilitator takes participants on a walk where they will use their senses and have short discussions.

3. Reflection & Wrap-Up (8 min)

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